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ANNUAL REPORT FISCAL YEAR 1982

**Pacific Marine Environmental Laboratory
Seattle, Washington**

January 1983

**U.S. DEPARTMENT OF COMMERCE
Malcolm Baldrige, Secretary**

**NATIONAL OCEANIC AND ATMOSPHERIC ADMINISTRATION
John V. Byrne, Administrator**

**ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH LABORATORIES
Boulder, Colorado
George H. Ludwig, Director**

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INTRODUCTION

The Pacific Marine Environmental Laboratory (PMEL) is a mission-oriented government laboratory located in Seattle, Washington, and is engaged in conducting research in oceanography, marine meteorology, and related subjects. Its research goal is to improve our understanding of environmental processes in both coastal and open-ocean systems in support of NOAA's mission to ensure the wise development and rational conservation of ocean resources and to monitor and predict weather and environmental conditions. The PMEL program focuses on the Pacific Ocean and adjacent coastal regions. Studies are conducted to understand better the complex physical and geochemical processes that determine the extent of human impact on the marine environment; to define the forcing functions and determine the time and space scales of the processes driving ocean circulation and the global climate system; and to improve environmental forecasting capabilities and other supporting services for marine commerce, fisheries, and recreation. Products of PMEL's research are environmental information and predictive models. These are disseminated by means of scientific papers, technical reports, and presentations to other researchers, NOAA operational elements, and interested local and Federal agencies.

Figure 1 Pacific Marine Environmental Laboratory organizational Chart.

This research requires a scientific staff with a broad range of disciplinary backgrounds, a strong technical support staff, and a research approach that integrates field, laboratory, and analytical efforts. The staff is organized into six research groups sharing a disciplinary or technical focus (fig. 1). The interdisciplinary projects constituting most of PMEL's activity

cut across the group structure and are coordinated by project managers designated within the Laboratory. PMEL research projects are elements of larger national or international programs, and staff scientists are consequently active in the broader oceanographic research community, serving on scientific steering committees and collaborating in multi-institutional field efforts. Cooperative research institutes established between NOAA and the Universities of Washington and Hawaii provide close research collaboration as well as opportunities for PMEL scientists to teach and supervise graduate student research through affiliate faculty appointments.

The assemblage of NOAA personnel and activities in Seattle is the second largest in the United States and includes elements of the National Weather Service (NWS), National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS), and National Ocean Survey (NOS). PMEL's proximity to these groups provides a unique opportunity for cooperative work and exchange of information, direct transfer of research results from PMEL to the operational components of NOAA, and ready access to major NOAA facilities such as the NOS Pacific Fleet, the National Analytical Facility, the Northwest Calibration Center, and the Seattle Ocean Services Unit.

OVERVIEW OF THE PMEL PROGRAM

Fiscal year 1982 was a year characterized for NOAA by organizational change and refocusing of scientific programs. These changes were reflected at PMEL through the departure of our first permanent director and further reductions in personnel and budgets. PMEL's response to decreased resources was to protect core programs in each research area and to eliminate peripheral projects. As a result of this restructuring, PMEL has emerged as a stronger, better-focused laboratory.

During fiscal year 1982, PMEL's scientific program was concentrated in four major areas that correspond to NOAA's areas of interest in oceanography: Marine Environmental Quality, Ocean Climate Dynamics, Marine Observation and Prediction, and Marine Resources. The mission of the Pacific Marine Environmental Laboratory is to conduct coordinated oceanographic and meteorological research to improve understanding of marine geochemistry, ocean circulation, and ocean-atmosphere interactions. This research is carried out in support of national programs within NOAA and other government agencies. Developed under the guidance of the PMEL Science Policy Board and the ERL Office of Programs, the PMEL Five-Year Plan summarizes the Laboratory's scientific plans for the period 1980-1985. The Five-Year Plan also defines goals and objectives for each program area and includes a projection of required resources, such as personnel, ship time, computers, and capital equipment.

PROGRAM AREAS

Within PMEL's four program areas are twelve elements (fig. 2), highlighted in the following sections of the Annual Report. The individual elements are integrated and redirected as necessary as the Laboratory's five-year research plan is implemented.

MARINE ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY

Marine environmental quality, the most diverse area of PMEL research, emphasizes understanding the complex physical and geochemical processes that ultimately determine the health of the marine system and its ability to assimilate potential pollutants. Included in this area are studies of

Figure 2 PMEL program areas.

suspended-sediment transport and geochemistry, distributions of hydrocarbons and synthetic organics, coastal and estuarine circulation, and theoretical modeling of pollutant transport processes.

The results of marine environmental quality research support NOAA's mission to provide timely information on the state of the marine environment to assist public decision makers in balancing economic development and environmental conservation. This service is critical in coastal and estuarine areas where an increasing assortment of both natural and synthetic materials enters the marine environment. Under the Marine Protection, Research and Sanctuaries Act of 1972 and the National Ocean Pollution Research and Development and Monitoring and Planning Act of 1978, NOAA has responsibility for monitoring and conducting research on ocean waste disposal and for coordinating Federal research programs in ocean pollution. Within this context, the PMEL program addresses environmental concerns associated with offshore oil development, transport and marine disposal of municipal waste water, and the reaction of marine systems to continuous influx of pollutants. PMEL research has been used to assess both the fate of potential oil spills in the Strait of Juan de Fuca arising from the Northern Tier proposal and the fate of potential spills associated with outer continental shelf oil and gas leasing. Under the NOAA Long-Range Effects Research Program, PMEL

is examining the role of suspended particulates in transporting pollutants or in removing them from the marine system. Researchers are also studying the mechanisms by which heavy metals and organic pollutants adhere to particulates. As these processes become better understood, we will be able to assess the long-term effect of chronic, low-level input of pollutants into the marine system.

OCEAN CLIMATE DYNAMICS

During recent years there has been an increasing awareness of the impact of short and long-term climatic changes on human systems, particularly food and energy, and conversely, a concern about the impact of technology and population growth on world climate. When the National Climate Program Act was passed in 1978, NOAA became the lead agency for U.S. research in climate dynamics. PMEL scientists have been heavily involved in the formulation and implementation of the NOAA Ocean Climate Program.

To predict climatic change, it is necessary to understand the processes of heat, moisture, and momentum exchange between the ocean and atmosphere, as well as the large-scale advection of heat by the atmosphere and ocean. The PMEL ocean climate dynamics program investigates the problem in studies of both local (small-scale) and basin-wide (large-scale) boundary layer dynamics and the coupled ocean-atmosphere circulation. Laboratory participation in multi-institutional field experiments — the Mixed Layer Experiment (MILE) in the North Pacific, the Joint Air-Sea Interaction Experiment (JASIN) off the coast of Scotland, the Coastal Upwelling Ecosystems Analysis (CUEA) Program in the southeast Pacific, the North Pacific Experiment (NORPAX) in the central tropical Pacific, and the PMEL equatorial program (EQUA) in the equatorial Pacific — has established the groundwork for present efforts in the NOAA Equatorial Pacific Ocean Climate Studies (EPOCS). These studies are testing the hypothesis that ocean surface temperature anomalies in equatorial regions have a pronounced effect on atmospheric circulation in both upper and lower latitudes. A major research goal is to determine the relative importance of the physical mechanisms that generate anomalies in sea

surface temperature distributions in the equatorial ocean.

Heat transport by major western boundary currents, the Gulf Stream and Kuroshio in the Northern Hemisphere, are also postulated to have an important impact on world climate. Studies during 1982 focused on the Florida Current as part of the Subtropical Atlantic Climate Study (STACS) and the Kuroshio in the vicinity of the Emperor Seamounts. These two studies will provide insight into the fluctuations of two of the world's major currents.

PMEL is also conducting two unique marine-chemistry research activities for NOAA under the National Climate Program. These activities relate to the ocean's behavior as a sink for atmospheric carbon dioxide, which has been steadily increasing over the past century. One project measures the flux of human-made fluorocarbons into the ocean in order to trace gaseous diffusion across the ocean-atmosphere boundary. The other project is examining the role of biologically produced, particulate calcium carbonate as an absorber of carbon dioxide at high latitudes. Together these studies will help determine the potential of the oceans for absorbing carbon dioxide.

OCEAN SERVICES RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

The goal of the PMEL program in ocean services is to improve NOAA's capabilities for providing information, forecasts, and warnings of possible environmental hazards to people in the offshore and coastal areas of the United States. PMEL scientists, in conjunction with personnel from NOAA operational elements, have identified priority areas where directed research can provide substantial improvement in marine forecasting and prediction. Research under way in 1982 was aimed at predicting the movement of the Bering Sea ice edge, predicting coastal wave conditions at harbor entrances, and improving tsunami forecasts and warnings in the Pacific Basin. The U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, the U.S. Coast Guard, the U.S. Navy, the Ocean Services Unit within the Seattle office of the National Weather Service, and the Pacific Tsunami Warning System will be among the direct users of this information.

MARINE RESOURCES

PMEL participates in research activities that provide information for resource management decisions by NOAA and other agencies. Building on past experience with ocean minerals in the Deep Ocean Mining Environmental Study (DOMES), PMEL fielded a small pilot study of geochemical plumes associated with polymetallic sulfides (PMS) in FY-1982. These metalliferous deposits may someday provide a rich source of ore for domestic processing and use.

PMEL has also begun planning and coordinating with the National Marine Fisheries Service for a joint research effort on oceanographic effects in the Bering Sea on a commercially important species, the king crab.

MAJOR RESEARCH ACCOMPLISHMENTS CLIMATE DYNAMICS

• The season-ahead predictions of temperature and precipitation over the U.S. mainland made by four separate forecast groups were statistically compared with observations with the following results: (1) *Temperature* over the U.S. mainland, as a function of either season or region, was better predicted than precipitation (during 1974-1982). (2) It was on average easier to predict temperature and precipitation in winter than in summer. (3) *Temperature* was better predicted, as a rule, for the Pacific Coast, Southwestern Desert, and Northern Plains areas. It was less well predicted in the Southern Plains, Gulf Coast, and along the Atlantic Coast (4) *Precipitation* was better predicted, as a rule, in the Southwestern Desert, Northern Great Basin, and Great Lakes areas, and was less well-predicted in Southern Plains, on the Gulf Coast, and along the Atlantic Coast.

• A prototype Electric Field Data Acquisition System was installed on the east Florida coast near Jupiter, Florida, in sup-

port of the STACS program. The system consists of two pairs of electrodes separated by 800 m and a fluxgate magnetometer with recording equipment. The electrodes sense a small electric potential induced by the offshore Florida Current. Readings from the magnetometer are used to remove signals arising from the earth's magnetic field. The remaining signal is then transformed into a measure of the Florida Current transport.

• Two major interdisciplinary studies of the dynamics of the North Pacific carbon dioxide system demonstrate that fossil-fuel-derived carbon dioxide has penetrated to depths of 500 to 1300 m, with the deepest penetrations occurring in the western North Pacific. The uptake of carbon dioxide by the oceans over the past 130 years has resulted in an apparent reduction in the thickness of the supersaturated surface waters and an upward translation of the 100% saturation level for aragonite by 70 m in regions north of the Subarctic Front.

• A system to strip freons from discrete water samples taken at sea was designed and fabricated. A commercial microprocessor-based controller was linked to a series of valves and temperature controllers to strip and prepare samples for injection to a gas chromatograph. This semiautomatic mode of laboratory analysis greatly reduces the work load of technicians and assures uniformity in the handling of replicate samples. Freons can be used to trace water mass sinking and movement in the deep oceans, information of importance to climate studies.

• Studies of the equatorial Pacific proceeded with sometimes unexpected results. Contrary to expectations, no statistically significant coherence was found between temperature measurements and computed vertical motion at a depth of 20 m. Southward displacement of the Intertropical Convergence Zone during normal years reduces the transport of the North Equatorial Countercurrent (NECC); however, similar, but more pronounced displacement during periods of the El Niño phenomenon are correlated with large NECC transport. These and other experimental results clearly demonstrate the need both for more experiments and for further theoretical development.

- Studies of currents near the Equator demonstrate that currents which agree well with directly measured currents can indeed be computed from the geostrophic approximation. Thus, even at the Equator, the force associated with the Earth's rotation remains a dominant term in the equations of motion.
- Analysis of data collected near Bermuda during the Local Dynamics Experiment identifies waters whose probable origin is the northwest coast of Africa. The minimal amount of mixing of this water suggests that mesoscale mixing is not as intense as hypothesized by theoretical studies of quasi-geostrophic turbulence.
- Field studies of the Kuroshio Current near the Emperor Seamounts began this year. A surprising result was the discovery, to the north of the main current, of a second jet whose transport is 80% of the main current. The presence of the second jet raises the question whether the Kuroshio branches west of the Emperor Seamounts or whether there is a separate current that can be related to the wind field.
- A comparison of three independent current profiling techniques yielded good agreement between techniques, thus enhancing our confidence in each. The techniques involved use of (1) the free-fall velocity profiling vehicle (TOPS), tracked in a moored acoustic array, (2) TOPS data analyzed by a hydrodynamic model without input from the acoustic array, and (3) the Expendable Current Profiler.

MARINE ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY

- Removal of particles from the surface waters of Puget Sound by settling was estimated to be 6×10^{11} , an amount roughly equal to the combined annual sediment input of the Puyallup and Duwamish Rivers.
- Once in the bottom layer, particles are episodically resuspended and moved by tidal currents. When the current exceeds 40 cm/s, the concentration of suspended particles near the bottom increases by a factor of six. Total annual flux in the deepest layer is 9.5×10^{11} g southward. This is approximately equal to the amount added to the deep layer by settling.

- Both manganese and iron were found to be rapidly remobilized in the sediments, forming hydrous oxides in the water column to which trace metals are absorbed and settle out. This recycling of manganese and iron is thought to be an important mechanism for the transport to the bottom and subsequent burial of trace metals.
- Studies of sediment cores from Puget Sound demonstrate that some activities of man have been recorded in the sediments. For example, a concentration maximum for PAH (polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons) was found at the stratum of the 1940's, with lessening amounts in more recent sediments. This coincides with the change from coal to oil, gas, and electricity in home heating. Although not as pronounced, the complex mixture of branched and cyclic alkanes (UCM) and the normal alkanes show maxima near 1965, when Seattle ceased dumping raw sewage into Puget Sound.
- Tidal current models tuned by observed tidal currents were developed which accurately predict the vertical profile of tidal currents. The best profiles were derived using a form of viscosity based on the turbulent energy equation.
- A numerical potential-vorticity model of circulation over the Kodiak Shelf shows that local circulation is strongly influenced by topography: streamlines follow the isobaths. This result is in good agreement with direct current measurements.

MARINE OBSERVATION AND PREDICTION

- Studies of hazardous waves at the Columbia River bar confirm that refraction by currents is the primary physical

mechanism of wave-height amplification. Amplifications in excess of 40% were observed during ebb currents of 2 ms^{-1} (4 kn). Currents observed at mid-channel (at 7 m depth) five miles from the river entrance agreed with the tidal current prediction tables. However, surface currents at the entrance exceeded up-river values by 20%.

- Results from the Puget Sound Wind Study were transferred to NWS, and a guide to marine weather of Washington was produced. Included in the guide is a set of composite surface wind and wind persistence field representations for the inland waters of western Washington keyed to the wind direction at 850 mb as measured on the coast at Quillayute, Washington.
- PMEL convened a workshop with the National Weather Service, the University of Washington, the Prototype Regional Observation and Forecasting System, and the Atmospheric Environmental Service of Canada to discuss barriers to further improvements in regional forecasts. As a result of this workshop, the UW in cooperation with NWS is designing a data collection and processing system for analysis and forecasting in the Puget Sound region.
- Experiments in 1982 demonstrate for the first time that sea ice generated in the Bering Sea can travel north into the Chukchi Sea during winter.
- Analysis of 1981 data revealed velocities among the largest ever measured for sea ice (0.5 m s^{-1}). Tidal currents influenced ice movement as did atmospheric drag. We attribute the large ice velocities to the validity of the free-drift assumption.
- Studies in the polynya south of St. Lawrence Island show that brine rejection during ice formation alters the salinity content of the polynya, thereby altering the circulation.

FUNDING

PMEL operations are supported by a combination of NOAA operations, research, and facilities funding (both one-time and permanent), and reimbursable funding from other agencies. During FY-1982 recurring NOAA-based funding accounted for 45% of the Laboratory support, one-time NOAA funding constituted 41% and reimbursable funding 14% (fig. 3). Support to universities, and in particular the cooperative institutes, was 10% of the PMEL budget.

GEOCHEMISTRY

HERBERT C. CURL, JR.

The Geochemistry Group conducts research on the origin, transport, and transformation of natural and man-made substances in both oceanic and estuarine environments, emphasizing substances that are marine or atmospheric contaminants or tracers of water movement. An interdisciplinary approach is used in the study of biogeochemical processes that affect the production and transport of trace gases, trace metals, and organic compounds. An important aspect of these studies is cooperative work with PMEL physical and theoretical oceanographers to determine residence times and dispersion rates resulting from circulation and mixing processes. The dynamics of mixing and heat transport in the oceans are being investigated with chemical tracers such as freon and methane.

CLIMATE PREDICTABILITY CARBON DIOXIDE IN THE OCEANS

The long-term increase in atmospheric carbon dioxide caused by the burning of fossil fuels beginning around 1800 is thought to be affecting the Earth's radiation balance and thereby increasing the Earth's temperature. Because the oceans act as a major sink for atmospheric carbon dioxide particularly in areas of downwelling where surface waters descend below 100 m, PMEL sponsored two interdisciplinary studies of the dynamics of the carbon dioxide system in the surface and intermediate waters of the North Pacific during fiscal years 1981 and 1982. The purpose of these studies was to determine the penetration and reactivity of fossil carbon dioxide in these waters. Measurements of total carbon dioxide, alkalinity, freons, tritium, calcium, and suspended matter were made during three north-south transects of the North Pacific aboard the NOAA Ships *Miller Freeman* and *Discoverer* (fig. 4). The results of these studies indicate that fossil carbon dioxide has penetrated to depths between 500 and 1300 m in the region, with the deeper penetrations occurring in the western North Pacific. The data have also been used to determine the effect of fossil carbon dioxide on the calculated degree of saturation of these waters with respect to calcium carbonate minerals. Uptake of fossil carbon diox-

Figure 4 Locations of the stations occupied during the two Marine CO₂ Dynamics Cruises aboard the *Miller Freeman* (June-July 1981) and the *Discoverer* (May-June 1982).

Figure 5 Percent aragonite saturation in the northeast Pacific along 150°W longitude. The dashed line shows the location of the preindustrial 100% saturation horizon.

ide by the oceans over the past 130 years has resulted in a significant change in the carbonate chemistry of the North Pacific Ocean. These results indicate an apparent reduction in the thickness of the supersaturated lenses and upward translation of the 100% saturation level by as much as 70 m for aragonite in the region north of the Subarctic Front (fig. 5). Since our sediment trap studies have shown that aragonite, from pteropods (planktonic marine molluscs), is the major solid contributing to the carbonate flux in these waters, in-situ dissolution reactions involving aragonite particles play an important role in the neutralization of fossil carbon dioxide in the North Pacific.

The chlorofluoromethanes (freons), trichlorofluoromethane (F-11), and dichlorodifluoromethane (F-12) are gaseous tracers of anthropogenic origin. Their historical release into the atmosphere has provided oceanographers with a valuable new chemical tracer with which to investigate mixing and circulation processes in the ocean. The near-exponential growth of these gases in the atmosphere parallels similar growth patterns of fossil-fuel-derived carbon dioxide; thus, the freons can be used in a direct way to estimate excess carbon dioxide inventories and mean penetration depths. More importantly, freons provide a quantitative measure of diffusion and convective mixing scales.

In the early summer of 1982, observations were made of the distributions of freons in the western Pacific. This region is known for its sharp contrasts in water masses and deep mixing characteristics; thus, it remains a principal locus for the assimilation of fuel-derived carbon dioxide. The distribution of F-11 is shown in figure 6. Salient features include the penetration of F-11 within and below the subtropical mode water and strong horizontal gradients near the Subarctic Front at 42°N. It is noteworthy that the freons are associated with the Intermediate Water (low salinity) in the western Pacific, but were not found in the same water mass in the eastern Pacific. From this distribution, estimates can be made of vertical diffusive and advective scales, and when coupled with tritium and carbon-14 (bomb tracers), provide estimates of circulation times within the subtropical mode water and ventilation rates of the North Pacific Intermediate Water.

Figure 6 Distribution of freon-11 on a transect along 165°E longitude. Units are picomoles per liter (10^{-12} M/L).

MARINE RESOURCES POLYMETALLIC SULFIDES

Recent investigations of seafloor volcanic vents have discovered metal deposits in the form of sulfides which are potential sources of several metals of importance to the U.S. economy. Geochemical investigations of hydrothermal venting systems, which are sometimes associated with polymetallic sulfide deposits, have been conducted by PMEL oceanographers during the past two years. These studies are designed to improve our understanding of the characteristics of sulfide formation and location of deposits. Near-bottom water samples have been collected along the axis of the Juan de Fuca Ridge from its juncture with the Blanco Fracture Zone to the Cob Offset and along the northern 150 km of the Gorda Ridge (fig. 7). Along with measurements of the standard hydrographic variables, samples have been analyzed for methane, dissolved manganese, total dissolvable manganese, and the elemental composition of suspended matter. The

Figure 7 Oceanographic stations occupied during the past two years for the collection of samples from water overlying the Juan de Fuca and Gorda Ridges and from background regions.

Figure 8 Vertical profiles of particulate manganese from enriched waters overlying Juan de Fuca and Gorda Ridge and from an open-ocean "background" station.

manganese data have been particularly useful in the search for regions of active venting because the emanating hydrothermal solutions are rich in dissolved manganese. Upon mixing with seawater, manganese undergoes a transition to the particulate phase and, in the process, becomes a likely scavenger for other trace metals. The several hundred meters of near-bottom water over both ridge systems display an enrichment of particulate manganese greater than fifteen-fold relative to open ocean values (fig. 8). Similar elevated manganese concentrations have been measured over other active venting regions such as the Galápagos Spreading Center and the East Pacific Rise and have been related to hydrothermal sources.

AIR QUALITY ACID RAIN

During the past year, PMEL has initiated research on the oceanic sources of acid rain precursors since these materials provide the background to which the industrial signal is added on the West Coast. One precursor, dimethylsulfide (DMS), is the most abundant reduced-sulfur compound present in the biologically rich surface waters of the oceans. DMS diffuses from the ocean to the atmosphere where it is oxidized to sulfur dioxide and ultimately precipitated as sulfuric acid. The goal of the project is to quantify the ocean contribution of naturally produced acid rain precursors.

DMS concentrations were recently measured on a cruise to the central equatorial Pacific Ocean. Background concentrations of DMS were approximately 80 ng/l in the subtropical gyre, but increased to 430 ng/l near the Equator (fig. 9), a value as high as any reported in the ocean. Depth distributions of DMS along the Equator showed a subsurface maximum at 20-40 m and decreased exponentially to undetectable concentrations below 150 m. Concentrations in the subsurface maximum decreased along the Equator (148°W to 170°E) from 390 to 100 ng/l. These measurements were used to estimate the flux of DMS in the central equatorial Pacific from 150°W to 170°E. Assuming that upwelling occurred along a 4° zone (2°N to 2°S), the flux of DMS to the atmosphere is 0.3 TG/yr. The flux, about 1% of the estimated global flux, originates from 0.6% of the ocean's surface. Additional measurements on future cruises will allow us to extrapolate the flux calculation to the entire Pacific Ocean.

POLLUTANT TRANSPORT PROCESSES

Research in fiscal year 1982 on pollutant transport centered on the patterns of circulation controlling the transport and distribution of particles (or pollutants) in two very different environments — Puget Sound, a complex urban estuarine system on the coast of Washington State, and the southeastern Bering Sea shelf off the northern coast of the Alaska Peninsula. The net circulation of particles is significantly different from that of the water itself because of sources and sinks such as erosion and deposition, and because of the gravitationally accelerated vertical particle movement of large, rapidly settling particles from surface to bottom water layers.

Figure 9 Surface seawater dimethylsulfide concentrations as a function of latitude.

Figure 10 Time series showing the relationship between current speed and resuspension of fine particles in the main basin of Puget Sound. Model predictions are superimposed on field data for two observational periods.

PUGET SOUND RESEARCH

In Puget Sound, most particles in the seaward-flowing surface layer are removed to the landward-flowing bottom water by two processes: (1) biological aggregation and settling, and (2) downward mixing (over Admiralty Inlet) and entrainment into the landward-flowing deep layer. Removal of particles from the surface by settling over the entire main basin, the large basin to the west of the city of Seattle, was estimated from sediment trap studies at 6×10^{11} g, an amount roughly equal to the combined annual sediment input of the Puyallup and Duwamish Rivers.

Once particles are removed to the deep layer, the net landward circulation tends to move them toward the southern terminus of the main basin. Particles in the bottom water are episodically moved by alternating periods of erosion and deposition. Field data show that diurnal and semidiurnal tidal currents with a combined speed near 40 cm/s raise concentration levels as much as 6-fold over the background concentration of approximately 1 mg/l (fig. 10). A preliminary comparison with a process model for tidally forced resuspensions suggests that the resuspended material has a bimodal settling spectrum, with coarser material (settling velocity of 0.1 cm/s) causing rapid changes in concentration against a more slowly changing background of fine particulates. Bottom sediments are reworked to a depth of about 0.2 cm over tidal cycle under these conditions.

Direct measurements of the horizontal flux in the deep layer were carried out for over a year at a single location in the main basin. These measurements indicate that the southward sediment flux is about 9.5×10^{11} g yr⁻¹, roughly equal to the amount of material introduced to the deep layer by vertical settling. The emerging picture is one of pronounced sediment mobility and rapid mixing of particles throughout the estuarine system.

Methane is normally found in the marine environment as a consequence of anaerobic respiration. When produced in significant quantities, such as found in anoxic basins or in organic-rich fjords, it may be used qualitatively as a tracer of circulation trajectories and in a quantitative way to characterize the mean current field and mixing rates.

Figure 11 The distribution of dissolved methane along the axis of the main basin, Puget Sound, in May 1980. Methane-deficient water intruded over the sill at Admiralty Inlet and penetrated southward to near Seattle. The distribution south of Seattle suggests weak circulation below 50 m.

The distribution of dissolved methane in the main basin of Puget Sound shows generally elevated concentrations at depth (fig. 11). The intrusion of methane-deficient water over the sill at Admiralty Inlet is also quite evident and serves to extend our tracer capability in the deeper water of the main basin. Methane is produced from microbial metabolic processes in organic-rich sediments and diffuses vertically into the basin waters. The distribution, which changes seasonally, represents a balance between the source at the bottom and the effects of diffusion and microbial oxidation. It appears that circulation was weak in the southern main basin at the time of measurement.

BERING SEA RESEARCH

Studies along the north side of the Aleutian Peninsula were conducted to determine the potential role of particulates in transporting spilled crude oil. The vertical distribution of water properties over the southeastern Bering Sea

Shelf is known to define three structurally distinct hydrographic domains separated by fronts where horizontal property gradients are steep. Recent investigations into the distribution of suspended particles have characterized domains and fronts analogous to those defined by the hydrography (fig. 12). The coastal domain (depth $< \sim 50\text{m}$) is typified by vertically homogenous particle concentrations and size distributions caused by vigorous wind and tidal stirring. In the middle domain, particle distributions are three-layered, with high turbidity layers at the surface (phytoplankton detritus) and bottom (resuspended sediments) separated by a thick minimum turbidity zone of weak horizontal and vertical gradients. These domains are separated by a particle front which is expressed in the surface and bottom waters as a particle concentration minimum and in the mid-depth region as a pronounced horizontal gradient in particle concentration and size distribution. Other particle minimum zones (fronts), located seaward of the middle domain, are associated with both surface and bottom water regions where the horizontal density gradient is steep.

Figure 12 Distribution of particulate matter as determined by light attenuation measurement (upper) as compared to the distribution of density (lower) on the North Aleutian shelf.

During a one-year study of the circulation of the southeastern Bering Sea, methane was used as a tracer of circulation along the North Aleutian Shelf and in the bottom waters of St. George Basin. In both cases, methane (CH_4) arose from localized biological sources. The depth-averaged, background-corrected, distribution of dissolved methane in August 1980 between Port Moller and Port Heiden is depicted in figure 13. This figure also depicts the depth-averaged distribution of salinity which indicates that CH_4 is associated with the discharge of freshwater from Port Moller. Methane is largely contained within the coastal zone (depth 50 m) and moves northeasterly along the shelf. The distribution was simulated with a stationary, two-dimensional diffusion-

advection model in which lateral diffusion (y-direction) was balanced by horizontal advection (x-direction) and air-sea exchange. Strong tidal mixing in the coastal zone permitted the model to be depth averaged. Methane, which was transported to the coastal zone by tidal pumping, served as the upstream boundary condition. The results of the simulation indicate that the mean current trajectory was to the north-east at 3-5 cm/s, in agreement with current meter measurements of 1-6 cm/s. Although circulation and mixing processes are more complex than our model would suggest, the main features of the methane distribution model were observed.

POLLUTANT TRANSFORMATION AND FATE

At the present time, municipal and industrial waste effluents comprise the ninth largest input of freshwater to the Puget Sound region. Although these effluents are processed to conform to water quality standards, they still represent an important source of trace metals and organic toxicants, pollutants which may adversely affect local fisheries. Local concern over waste-water standards is a relatively recent phenomenon, and as recently as twenty years ago, before the opening of the West Point Sewage Treatment Plant in 1965, substantial quantities of untreated effluents were routinely discharged into Puget Sound. There are virtually no records of these discharges. In order to properly establish a budget for pollutants in the Puget Sound region (and thereby make possible forecasts of trends), we are using sediment cores to estimate the historical input of pollutants to the system.

HISTORIC DATA BASE

Work is presently underway to create a demographic, economic, and environmental data base that will provide some guidance on the likely input of pollutants over the last eight decades of the Puget Sound region's industrialization. The data base is organized by the region's principal watersheds, extended somewhat to accommodate the various municipal and industrial effluent discharge points. Data pertaining to

the various demographic characteristics of the watersheds' population are being culled from census records, and land use information has been obtained from a variety of sources, most importantly, Landsat imagery. Various federal and state agencies have been contacted to obtain relevant economic data such as gasoline consumption and motor vehicle registrations. These data are being archived in computer files, and software is presently being developed that will allow us to determine statistically significant relationships between

the many different parameters. These relationships will be used to extrapolate and interpolate the discontinuous and sporadic time series we are now acquiring.

SEDIMENT DATING

Pollutants are delivered to the sediment by horizontal transport and vertical deposition processes. The rate at which pollutants are accumulated in sediments, however, is a complex function of both the sedimentation and bioturbation (mixing) rates. Sedimentation and bioturbation signals must be separated from measured sediment constituent profiles before particle and pollutant budgets and/or models can be formulated. Geochemists under contract to PMEL are currently determining the lead (^{210}Pb) and thorium (^{234}Th) geochronologies for gravity cores, box cores, and Kasten cores collected from Puget Sound in an effort to resolve these processes. Sediment inventories for several trace metal and organic pollutants from these cores have been established.

TRACE METALS

During the past few years, PMEL scientists have also undertaken studies to provide an understanding of the transformations and fates of toxic trace elements and organic compounds in estuarine and coastal environments. These studies have focused on flocculation, scavenging, diagenesis, and remobilization processes in estuaries receiving municipal waste effluents.

In FY-1982, PMEL scientists completed a year-long sediment trap study in the main basin of Puget Sound, one purpose of which was to determine the seasonal and vertical variations of the fluxes of particulate trace elements associated with oxide, organic, and acid-resistant phases of suspended matter in the Sound. The results show that for iron, manganese, cobalt, zinc and lead, acid-resistant and organic phases controlled the vertical flux of copper and chromium. The cadmium flux was predominantly controlled by oxide and organic phases. For several trace elements, notably manganese, cobalt, chromium, nickel and zinc, the flux in the organic phase was higher in summer than in winter. The

Figure 13 The depth-averaged distribution of dissolved methane and salinity along the North Aleutian shelf in August 1980. An ambient background concentration of $0.4 \mu\text{M/L}$ has been subtracted from the concentration field. The inner front, located near the 45 m isobath, is indicated by a dashed line.

elemental flux data for winter show a slight decrease from the 50-m to the 100-m sediment trap followed by a striking increase in the sediment traps located at 160 m and 205 m, the increases being due to resuspension of bottom sediments. The elemental concentration data show that the sedimentary material from the 50-m and 100-m sediment traps are significantly elevated in manganese, zinc, and lead relative to the underlying sediments. These enrichments are attributed to formation of manganese and iron hydrous oxides in the water column and adsorption of trace metals on the newly formed oxide phases. This mechanism provides an important means for scavenging and removal of trace metals in Puget Sound. That both manganese and iron are rapidly remobilized in the underlying sediments suggests that the process is cyclic, with the hydrous oxides being major agents for trace metal transport to the bottom of the Sound.

In FY-1982 PMEL scientists initiated studies of trace element recycling processes in the underlying sediments. Pore-water samples were extracted and analyzed for nutrients, major and trace elements, and dissolved gases. In cooperation with University of Washington scientists, a Bottom Lander was deployed on the seabed in the main basin of Puget Sound to directly measure the fluxes of primary constituents across the sediment-seawater interface. The results suggest that the sediments are a major source for ammonia, phosphate, silica, manganese, alkalinity, and total carbon dioxide, and a major sink for oxygen. The concentrations of copper and cadmium in the interstitial porewaters are sufficiently low as to indicate that the sediments are not a major source for these metals.

TOXIC ORGANICS

During the past three years, PMEL has conducted research on the sources, transport, and distribution patterns of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) in Puget Sound. Many of these compounds are mutagenic and carcinogenic and thus pose a significant threat to the marine environment. The origins of these water-insoluble compounds are petroleum products and combustion processes; their modes

Figure 14 Distribution of pollutant hydrocarbons in a sediment core from the main basin of Puget Sound.

of entry are principally atmospheric deposition, riverine input, and waste-water discharge.

The distribution of PAH in the sediments of Puget Sound reflects the increased industrialization and urbanization of the area since the early 1900's. PAH concentrations in the sediments increase markedly between the turn of the century and the 1940's, and then decrease to present-day levels (fig. 14). The concentration maximum in the 1940's is probably related to the change in home heating fuels from coal to oil, gas, and electricity. The complex mixture of branched and cyclic alkanes (UCM), and the normal alkanes both show maxima, although not as pronounced, near 1965, the point at which Seattle terminated the dumping of raw sewage into the main basin of Puget Sound. Concentrations of PAH in sediment trap samples show significant differences between summer and winter, probably reflecting the amount of fuel oil used in seasonal home and commercial heating. Clearly, the industrial influences of man are reflected in the sedimentary record of organic compounds.

PLANS

- A major cruise combining observations for the marine carbon dioxide program and the Acid Rain program will take place in late spring 1983, occupying stations between Dutch Harbor, Alaska; Hawaii, San Diego; and Seattle. This cruise will provide a fourth line of stations in the North Pacific and reoccupy several GEOSECS stations.
- PMEL scientists expect to participate in a joint, interdisciplinary cruise in 1983 to explore for active hydrothermal venting on the Juan de Fuca Ridge and Gorda Rift. Chemical tracers will be analyzed aboard ship to map the distribution of vent plumes in quasi-real time. Areas of presumed venting will have been detected earlier by geophysical prospecting and photographic techniques.
- Observations of distributions of organic low-molecular-weight sulfur compounds (acid-rain precursors), primarily

dimethylsulfide, will be made on coastal transects between San Diego and Seattle in early summer of 1983. Correlations will be sought among concentrations of precursors, biological production, and solar radiation. Atmospheric measurement of precursor concentrations in the atmospheric boundary layer will be made to assess the rate of evasion of these substances from the ocean.

- A major experiment will be performed in Puget Sound to determine the bulk transport of water, suspended particulate matter, and related pollutants in an area presumed to be the final resting place of pollutants introduced into the Sound.

- In FY-1983 we propose to continue to explore the rates of accumulation of sediments by expanding our use of geochronometers to include long-lived isotopes (239 , 240 Pu) to delineate deep-mixing processes, by examining natural sedimentation horizons using physical techniques (visual/textural searches for ash layers in deep cores) and the available

geophysical records (seismic profiles), and by comparing sediment pollutant inventories with demographic data (pollutant source strength and time relationships with sediment column profiles).

- We will continue our studies of trace element and PAH fluxes in Puget Sound. These data will provide a basis for determining the relative importance of several possible removal mechanisms for these toxic pollutants in coastal waters. Work will continue on trace element recycling processes in the underlying sediments. Emphasis will be placed on processes occurring in the southern main basin, a region of fine-grained sediment accumulation, where the largest buildup of trace metals in sediments has been observed.

- Research on the fate of organic pollutants and trace metals will focus on burial and transformation processes and on relating concentration profiles in the sedimentary record to historical events in the surrounding watersheds.

COASTAL PHYSICS GLENN A. CANNON

The Coastal Physics Group conducts research on the physical processes that control structure and motion in coastal and estuarine marine environments. Field programs and theoretical research focus on the processes that drive marine circulation and result in the redistribution of natural and man-made substances.

FLUID TRANSPORT PROCESSES

Fluid transport processes affecting the distribution and fate of contaminants are a central focus for studies relating to marine environmental quality. Scientists in the Coastal Physics Group are addressing this topic under the aegis of two large NOAA programs — the Outer Continental Shelf Environmental Assessment Program (OCSEAP) and the Long-Range Effects Research Program (L-RERP). Studies for OCSEAP have been aimed at defining spatial and temporal variations of general circulation in the broad shelf areas of the Bering Sea and northern Gulf of Alaska and relating circulation patterns to potential oil spill movement. In the more populous Puget Sound and Strait of Juan de Fuca region, research supported both by PMEL based funds and by L-RERP has emphasized studies of the physical transport processes critical to defining the capacity of the marine system to accommodate municipal waste discharges or accidental spills from tanker traffic. International studies have been carried out in the Sulu Sea and in the Yangtze River estuary and adjacent continental shelf.

BERING SEA CIRCULATION

In the last few years a great deal of interest has focused on the impact of salinity enhancement caused by brine rejection during ice formation. This process alters both flow and water properties. Salinity is generally thought to be increased by wind-driven surface divergence. The process of salinity enhancement begins with the creation, by the wind, of local polynyas, essentially ice-free areas within an ice field. When the winds repeatedly remove ice in this manner, extremely large effective ice production is possible, with an accompanying large vertical salt flux. If the water is contained

Figure 15 Satellite photograph (visible band) of the northern Bering Sea, 3 March 1978. The darker areas of the sea (e.g., south of St. Lawrence Island, which is located at the base of the arrow pointing north) generally represent ice-free conditions.

in an appropriate reservoir, such as a shallow and broad shelf, its salinity can be enhanced significantly.

During the winter of 1980-81, we collected long-term (~ 230 day) measurements from three moorings in the vicinity of St. Lawrence Island on the northern Bering Sea shelf. One mooring was deployed near the polynya that often occurs south of the island (fig. 15). These data confirm the existence of strong ($\sim 0.15 \text{ ms}^{-1}$) flow toward the Bering Strait northwest of the island, in Anadyr Strait, and suggest that regional circulation results in a moderate ($\sim 0.035 \text{ ms}^{-1}$) mean flow eastward along the southern coast of St. Lawrence Island. Variations in the regional circulation and variations in the wind field were coherent with and accounted for many of the current fluctuations south of St. Lawrence Island. In addition, eleven events occurred when offshore wind coin-

cided with increasing salinity, decreasing water temperature, and reversal of the current. This suggests that ice formation and the ensuing brine rejection affect flow in the vicinity of the polynya.

Scaling of a simplified momentum equation indicates that the cross-shelf density gradient is a possible mechanism for some of these reversals. Salinity data show a seasonal cycle with an increase of about 1 g kg^{-1} , as well as individual events of brine rejection. During an average event time of 65 hr, the salinity increased by $8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ g kg}^{-1} \text{ hr}^{-1}$; the heat flux can be estimated as 535 W m^{-2} . These fluxes correspond to an ice production of 5 m per m^2 of water surface during winter 1981. Extrapolation of our results and comparison with the freshwater cycle suggest that brine rejection is an important component of the regional salt budget.

Tide models tuned by observed tidal currents have been developed to predict the vertical profiles of tidal currents (fig. 16). A comparison of profiles for different forms of the vertical viscosity shows that the viscosity that gives the most physically reasonable profiles for a wide variety of tidal regimes is the one based on the turbulent energy equation (using level-II, second-order closure). This form of viscosity works well for the tidal regimes in the Bering Sea where semidiurnal tidal currents occur near their critical latitudes, thus increasing the vertical extent of bottom boundary effects. For this case maximum bottom stress, as derived from a bottom roughness length parameter, was used to determine a viscosity profile, which in turn was used to construct theoretical current profiles. The theoretical current profile agrees well with observations. Other forms of viscosity become ambiguous in this case because these forms contain numerical coefficients that must be chosen arbitrarily.

ALASKAN STREAM TRANSPORT

Five current meters on two moorings in the Alaskan Stream off Kodiak Island were recovered, ending a year-long deployment designed to provide information on the shear and scale of features in the stream and on the energy transfer to shelf waters. Analysis of data from two cruises in the Stream (winter 1980 and summer 1981) reveals marked differences in the flow. The winter data (fig. 17) show a typical inflow of stream waters into the Gulf of Alaska and relatively constant transport from the head of the Gulf westward; the summer data indicated reduced transport in the eastern part of the area and a greater inflow across the southern boundary of the stream between 150° and 165°W. Earlier work did not reveal a correlation with transport and wind-stress curl integrated from the coast, but spatial differences in the local wind-stress curl (Ekman pumping effect) appear to ac-

count for the flow variations. This is the same mechanism previously found to induce seasonal variations in the flow of the Kuroshio. Thus a forcing function has been identified that can cause large changes in the Alaskan Stream, and further work will focus on the detailed features resulting from these fluctuations.

KODIAK SHELF CIRCULATION

A circulation regime in which the mean flow is strongly influenced by the complex topography has been identified on the Kodiak Shelf. A numerical potential-vorticity model shows that streamlines follow isobaths and form a cyclonic vortex, or Taylor column, over the Kiliuda Trough. This result is in good agreement with direct current measurements (see fig. 18). Areas of steeper topography concentrate streamlines, causing current speeds to be dependent, in part, on the local topographic gradient. The measured mean flow pattern did not change significantly between winter and summer in spite of drastic change in magnitude and direction of seasonally averaged local wind stress. Thus, instead of wind forcing, the Alaskan Stream boundary current is the dominant driving mechanism for the mean shelf flow.

PUGET SOUND CIRCULATION

The overall goal of research in Puget Sound has been to provide better descriptions and understanding of circulation and mixing processes important in determining the capacity of Puget Sound to accommodate municipal and industrial wastes from the growing urban complex. Toward this end, all available historic data on currents in Puget Sound from 1908-1980 have been collected (jointly with MESA and private consultants) for synthesis to better understand the flow variations. PMEL is directly responsible for about 50% of this data base.

Figure 19 Schematic circulation along Puget Sound showing previous stations (*), on which speculations on recirculation were based, and 1982 stations (vertical lines) which were designed to test the recirculation hypothesis.

A conceptual model of Puget Sound derived from earlier studies indicates that considerable seaward-flowing surface water mixes with new water entering the deep basin at the southern end of Admiralty Inlet, and that this mixture is refluxed into the Sound in the deep water below sill depth (fig. 19). Observations from Admiralty Inlet were used for a first approximation of the average flux through Admiralty Inlet which supported the conceptual model. Only about half as much water was entering the inlet as the average southward flow observed about midway along the main basin. However, the sets of observations were from different seasons and different years, and it was unclear whether the speculations might be false because of as yet unknown seasonal changes in the transport.

During this year observations were made to better determine a) the simultaneous flux of both water and sediment through sections in the main basin and on the Admiralty Inlet entrance sill and b) the downward entrainment or reflux of water in the entrance region where no previous measurements existed. In the lower 48 states, this downward mixing of seaward-flowing water is possibly unique to the Puget Sound estuary. Most other U.S. estuaries mix incoming water upward, which dilutes the seaward-flowing surface water. Puget Sound, however, is a fjord-type estuary and has greater similarities to the inlets of British Columbia and Alaska and to the fjords of Norway.

The implications of the potential refluxing of part of the seaward-flowing water are significant for the flushing of the Puget Sound main basin in the sense that some fraction of dissolved and suspended pollutants does not leave the basin. This fraction might make additional trips through the Sound and possibly lead to some unknown amount of long-term accumulations.

STRAIT OF JUAN DE FUCA TRANSPORT

Analyses were completed on a two-year data set obtained to examine and monitor interactions that occur between circulation in the Strait of Juan de Fuca and that of the adjacent continental shelf. The results confirm and complement previous research in the strait. The data set, along with satellite imagery, shows that surface intrusions of less-dense coastal water into the strait are a major, recurring feature of its general circulation. The intrusions, which are accompanied by reversals in the normally vigorous, two-layer estuarine flow, are correlated with southwesterly coastal winds (conducive to coastal downwelling) and rising sea level at the entrance. The phenomenon may be explained by a wind-induced, shoreward Ekman flux along the coast that pushes less-dense coast water into the strait and feeds a complex, 3-dimensional, density-driven flow that has been observed as far as 135 km up-strait.

INTERNATIONAL STUDIES

As a part of the Federal government, PMEL is occasionally called upon to assist in the foreign policy objectives of the United States. As part of a policy encouraging closer working relations with the People's Republic of China, PMEL participated in a study of sediment transport in the Yangtze River Estuary. En route to that area, we were also able to study massive internal waves in the Sulu Sea south of the Philippine Islands.

YANGTZE RIVER STUDIES

The Yangtze, one of the world's largest rivers, drains much of central China. In addition, it discharges onto one of the widest continental shelves in the world. Because of the importance of the Yangtze to China, a joint Chinese/American interdisciplinary study was initiated concerning sediment discharge and its distribution and effects on the East China Sea continental shelf. Field experiments were conducted in summer 1980 and in summer and fall 1981. The 1980 work included the NOAA Ship *Oceanographer*.

During high-runoff observations in June 1980, it was observed that upon exiting the Yangtze, the freshwater plume flowed to the east and north. In addition, suspended sediment concentrations in this offshore plume were very low, although they had been very high at the mouth of the Yangtze. The highest concentrations of suspended sediment were located on the south side of the river mouth and seemed to go southward. Also, earlier studies had shown that most of the modern bottom sediments were located at the Yangtze mouth and southward fairly near the shore. Thus, it was speculated that the Yangtze discharge might split upon exiting the river mouth, part going north and east, and part going south near the coast. A similar situation had been observed for Chesapeake Bay in the eastern U.S. To test this hypothesis for the Yangtze, three moorings, equipped with both Chinese and American current meters, were deployed during the August 1981 high-runoff study. Preliminary assessment of the southernmost mooring data (fig. 20) indicates that part of the Yangtze most likely does flow south, and

then returns northward inshore of the Taiwan warm current.

Figure 20 Current meter vector diagram and salinity observations from near surface at the site southeast of the mouth of the Yangtze River. Salinity shows occurrence of fresher water midway through the record and the currents indicate the water comes from the south; other data indicate it originates in the Yangtze

HEAT TRANSPORT EQUATORIAL SURFACE HEAT FLUX

A limited effort was conducted under the auspices of EPOCS to analyze radiation measurements and weather reports aboard the NOAA ships in the eastern tropical Pacific. The data were used to estimate heat budgets over limited regions; changes in upper-ocean heat content and the relevant terms in the heat budget were quite variable. In some cases surface exchanges and changes in heat content roughly balanced, but on other instances heat advection was a dominant process. Daily fluxes determined from these data had features and variability similar to those seen in long-term monthly and annual means. The surface heat fluxes have also been examined on a long-term basis. The specially edited 1970's ship-report data set was obtained for the eastern tropical Pacific, and heat fluxes and weather parameters were derived. Preliminary findings are that the seasonal cycle in sea surface temperature is not mainly controlled by variations in surface heat exchange, and that the thermal structure during a major El Niño is not significantly affected by variations in surface heat flux. A related task, deriving climatological estimates of precipitation for the world ocean, was essentially completed, and the distributions are in close agreement with those derived by the Kilonsky and Ramage technique for the tropics.

SULU SEA SOLITON ANALYSIS

From 6 May to 20 May 1980, time series measurements of currents and temperature at three mooring sites and ship-board acoustic, CTD, and XBT profiling were obtained in the Sulu Sea to study the propagation characteristics and generation mechanism of internal solitary waves (solitons) previously observed as striations in Defense Meteorological Satellite Program (DMSP) satellite imagery. Seventeen soliton packets were measured near the middle of the sea with characteristics of amplitude 10-90 m, half-amplitude length 2-3 km, wave length 5-8 km, period 35-55 min, phase velocity ~ 2.2 - 2.6 m/s, and horizontal currents ~ 0.2 - 1.0 m/s, making them among the largest and fastest internal waves ever re-

ported. Many of these parameters undergo change as the packets propagate northward across the Sulu Sea. Finite depth theory for nonlinear internal waves has been found to be generally in good quantitative agreement with the observations.

Figure 21 Schematic diagram summarizing the evolution of a soliton packet in the Sulu Sea. In the sill region, an internal hydraulic jump is produced by strong ebb (southward) flow over the Pearl Bank sill (a). As the tidal flow changes to weak flood, a broad thermocline depression moves over the sill and propagates northward (b). Eventually solitary waves begin to form on this depression as nonlinear and dispersive effects begin to balance (c). After traveling a distance of 200 km, the soliton packet is well developed (d).

Analyses conducted during 1982 suggest that the generation mechanism involves several stages (fig. 21). Initially, strong tidal flow (directed southward out of the Sulu Sea) creates a super-critical condition over a sharp sill near Pearl Bank and establishes a large hydraulic jump in its lee. As the tide turns, the hydraulic jump moves over the sill and propagates northward as a single shallow-water internal wave. Eventually on this broad thermocline depression, internal undulations begin to form that grow rapidly to evolve into a packet of internal solitons as nonlinear and dispersive effects come into balance. Then, in the convergence region over the descending portion of each soliton, bands of breaking, sur-

DEEP-SEA PHYSICS

BRUCE A. TAFT

The Deep-Sea Physics Group conducts research on the processes in the deep ocean that control the variability of momentum of ocean currents and the resulting transport of heat and salt. These studies involve both an extensive field program at sea for collecting data in the tropics and subtropics and the ongoing interpretation of these data by means of dynamical models.

STUDIES OF THE TROPICAL PACIFIC

Large interannual changes that occur in the heat content of the surface layer of the tropical Pacific are associated with large-scale fluctuations in atmospheric circulation. Our studies concern the effect of ocean mixing and circulation on ocean surface layer characteristics, through which we hope to begin to understand the causes of changes in upper-ocean heat content. Since the upper layer of the ocean is driven by exchanges of heat, water, and momentum with the atmosphere, the effects of the atmosphere on these upper-layer processes must be considered.

During the past year, our field program has included taking measurements of wind, currents, and temperature from deep-sea moorings at the Equator in the eastern Pacific; making north-south transects to measure velocity, temperature, salinity, and oxygen across the major components of the current system in the eastern Pacific; recording sea-level measurements at the Galápagos Islands; and analyzing ship-of-opportunity, sea surface temperature data in the tropical Pacific. These measurement programs were PMEL contributions to the EPOCS oceanographic program in the eastern Pacific. Studies of the following topics were completed during the year in conjunction with the EPOCS program.

EQUATORIAL UPWELLING AND SEA-SURFACE TEMPERATURE VARIATIONS

In the upper equatorial ocean, heat content is determined in part by upwelling, the process of vertical movement of water toward the surface. In the interior of the ocean, the magnitude of vertical motion beneath the layer of wind-driven horizontal currents is estimated to be small, approxi-

Figure 22 Mean vertical velocity distribution computed from the conservation of mass. Array configuration is shown in inset.

mately 10^{-5} to 10^{-6} cm s^{-1} . Because direct measurement of vertical motion anywhere in the ocean is extremely difficult, upwelling is usually inferred, with caution, from changes in the position of properties such as constant temperature layers or isotherms. Another method of determining upwelling is the analysis of spatial variation of horizontal currents, using the principle of conservation of mass, which requires that water entering a given volume of the ocean be equal to water leaving that volume. Thus, horizontal currents which converge (or diverge) must be accompanied by vertical currents to remove (or bring in) an equal amount of water.

Measurements from an array of current meter moorings at 110°W show the mean direction and velocity (w) of vertical movement (fig. 22). Between the surface and about 175 m, the mean vertical velocity was upward and its maximum value occurred near the core depth of the Equatorial Undercurrent, a major subsurface eastward current. The bottom depth of the near-surface upwelling zone was about the same as that found by other researchers through the analysis of tritium data. At 200 and 250 m, the mean vertical motion was directed downward. The observed reversal of w provides an explanation for the upward and downward spreading of the isotherms and oxygen isopleths (surfaces of equal concentration) frequently observed, respectively, above and below the core of the Undercurrent.

The persistent occurrences of relatively large biological

Figure 23 Low-frequency time variations of the 110°W temperature (—) and vertical velocities (----) at 20 m.

productivity and low sea-surface temperature in a narrow band along the Equator in the central and eastern Pacific are thought to be related to the upwelling of cold, nutrient-rich waters from the thermocline. However, at 20-m depth, no statistically significant relationship was found between the temperature observations and the computed vertical motion (fig. 23). Instead, the 10 to 15-day time-scale temperature fluctuations observed at 20 m were correlated with north-south velocity variations.

Further evidence that the role of upwelling in changing sea surface temperature is poorly understood is the following puzzle. If the thermocline were moving upward at $\sim 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ cm s^{-1} (as our estimates of w indicated), why did the mixed layer thickness remain unchanged and the temperature in the mixed layer gradually increase? One possible cause for this is the wind-induced divergence which can have two effects: it can cause entrainment of cold water across isotherms into the mixed layer, or it can raise the isotherms and decrease the depth of the mixed layer. However, the wind-stress was too small and the thermocline was too strong for wind-generated entrainment at the bottom of the mixed layer to be a significant process. Thus, the sea surface temperature fluctuations are clearly not simply related to vertical mixing and/or upwelling, but must involve heating or cooling by air-sea fluxes or gain or loss of heat through horizontal currents.

ZONAL (LONGITUDINAL) TRANSPORT ACROSS 110°W

Another area of interest has been east-west geostrophic transport across north-south lines into the eastern Pacific, by the North Equatorial Countercurrent (NECC), the Northern Subsurface Countercurrent (NSCC), and their relation to the Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ), a large area of convergence of northern and southern hemisphere trade winds. The seasonal variability of the transport is of particular interest. Our analysis of nine hydrographic sections from 10°N to 5°S along 110°W longitude shows that eastward geostrophic transport (computed relative to 500 db) north of the equator (fig. 24) reflects contributions from both NECC and NSCC. While the NECC indicated large seasonal variations with a range of $3 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ to $12 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, the NSCC transport was relatively constant at $14 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The variability of the NECC transport correlates with the position of the Intertropical Convergence Zone: NECC is weak in the northern spring when the ITCZ is southernmost and strong

Figure 24 Zonal transport ($10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) between 2° and 10°N along 110°W (EASTROPAC, 1967-1968, EPOCS, 1979-1981).

* El Niño is the large warming in the equatorial eastern Pacific accompanied by heavy rains and flooding and often commencing in mid-December, hence its name, El Niño (the child), after the Christ Child.

in the northern fall when the ITCZ is northernmost. This correlation of the annual NECC transport variability with the wind field substantiates previous analyses based on less data and raises an interesting question concerning the strength of the NECC during large interannual warming events, the so-called El Niño. * El Niño is associated with a large southward shift or displacement of the ITCZ, so we would expect a weak NECC during El Niño if the dynamics of both events are similar. However, historical data in the western and central Pacific suggest large NECC transport during El Niño. Understanding this apparent discrepancy will require monitoring by moored arrays during several annual cycles and at least one El Niño. Our study of spatial scales of the geostrophic currents indicates that long-term monitoring of the NECC/NSCC system can be achieved using an array of four moored thermistor chains.

DYNAMICS OF EQUATORIAL UNDERCURRENT

A study completed this year concerns the dynamics of the Equatorial Undercurrent. Most undercurrent models assume that there is a geostrophic balance between the Coriolis force and the meridional pressure force. (At the equator $q\beta u = p_{yy}$, where β is the meridional gradient of the Coriolis parameter, q is the density, and p_{yy} is the second meridional derivative of pressure.) This relationship was checked by using several sections of closely spaced CTD stations across the equator to estimate p_{yy} , and comparing the results with moored or profiling current measurements. As seen in figure 25, the geostrophically estimated current (i.e., current estimates derived from horizontal density differences) agrees quite well with the direct measurement except near the sea surface. The velocity change from the Undercurrent core (75-m depth) to the deepest current meter (250-m depth) was estimated with an error (rms) of about 15%. This agreement compares favorably with estimates of the error in mid-latitude geostrophic computations and constitutes the first demonstration of geostrophic balance at the Equator. Thus, even at the Equator, the force associated with the Earth's

Figure 25 Comparison of east-west velocity component measured by profiling current meter (---), current meter mooring (*), and computed from the geostrophic equation (—).

rotation, the Coriolis force, remains a dominant term in the equations of motion.

SEA-SURFACE TEMPERATURE PROFILES

We began the analysis of continuous records of sea surface temperature (SST) obtained from shipboard intake systems on EPOCS cruises (1979-1982). The thermograph temperatures were compared with bucket temperatures, and good agreement was found. The data show an annual temperature progression for the eastern equatorial SST minimum that agrees with other findings. Between March and June, the SST increased by more than 1°C, the temperature had begun to drop by June, and a minimum occurred in late October. In the five 1981 sections at 110°W that we analyzed, fronts of 2°C change over a distance of 20 km were found at approximately 3°N in the November and January data, but not in the February, March, and June tracks. The transition to the equatorial temperature minimum is characteristically much sharper to the north than to the south (fig. 26). Fronts detected in the ship intake records will be compared with satellite measurements of fronts to determine what atmospheric (heat flux) and

Figure 26 Meridional profile of sea-surface temperature across 110°W.

Figure 27 Neutral drag coefficient estimates C_{dn} compared with modeled values.

oceanographic (current) conditions exist when the fronts occur.

BOUNDARY LAYER STUDIES

Studies of the transfer of momentum between ocean and atmosphere during storm conditions in the Gulf of Alaska were carried out in the Storm Transfer and Response Experiment (STREX). During the investigation, the neutral atmospheric drag coefficient, C_{dn} , and ocean surface-wave spectra were measured on both sides of a strong atmospheric front. The front was part of a mature, extratropical cyclone moving across the Gulf of Alaska on 15 November 1980. A new finding was the large variation in C_{dn} at constant mean wind speed in the cold sector of the front.

Previous work, which attempted to relate drag coefficients to surface wind speed, ignored the effects of the coincident surface wave field. As a result, no explicit dependence of C_{dn} on the wave field has been reported. This investigation, which measured the complete energy spectrum for sur-

face waves, constitutes the first wave spectral measurements made together with stress measurements (by the eddy correlation flux method) in the marine surface layer. Coincident wave spectral measurements showed an unexpected increase in energy in the six-second wave band (0.15-0.17 Hz), which was correlated with the variation of C_{dn} . The spatial distribution of wave spectral energy in the duration-limited sea behind the 15 November front was found to differ markedly from the spatial distribution of wave spectral energy in the fetch-limited case. The wave spectra in the warm sector followed the classical model well. The wave spectra in the cold sector did not.

Using only the wave spectral information, we derived a representation of roughness length (z_0), which reduced to the usual relation in situations of dynamic equilibrium between the wind field and the surface waves. In situations of

disequilibrium between the wave field and the surface wind, the derived relation showed a dependence on z_0 relationship. The relationship of z_0 to the surface wave spectra helps explain the high values of C_{dn} behind moving fronts, which have been reported in the literature.

Figure 27 shows the comparison of the neutral drag coefficient calculated using only wave spectral information and C_{dn} measured with an aircraft gust-probe system.

MESOSCALE EDDIES AND THE GENERAL CIRCULATION

One of the critical elements in the development of successful models of the general ocean circulation is the correct parameterization of the transfer of heat and momentum in the ocean. An intensive study of ocean eddies was carried out in 1978 near Bermuda (POLYMODE Local Dynamics Experiment) to advance our understanding of the role of eddies in the transport of heat and momentum in the ocean.

Analysis of temperature, salinity, density, and dissolved oxygen data has revealed the presence of relatively small (25-50 km) horizontal-scale and thin (100-1000 m) water mass anomalies with a large signal. Profiles of salinity against density obtained in one of these features with an anomalously low salinity are shown in figure 28. The dashed lines show the two limits of the standard deviation envelope so that the maximum anomaly departs from the mean of the experiment by 8 standard deviations. These features, and most others, normally have a dynamical structure and thus have a circulation which is different from the background. Study of particular features shows that they are moved by the large-scale flow and are not self-propelled. Tracing of the probable origin of the water in this feature suggests that it came from the northwest coast of Africa and mixed only slightly with its surroundings en route. The occurrence of these eddies suggests that mixing on the mesoscale is not as intense as hypothesized by theoretical studies of quasi-geostrophic turbulence. New formulations of mixing are being explored.

WESTERN BOUNDARY CURRENTS

Interaction of strong currents and bottom topography is thought to be important in the transfer of energy from large to small scales and the ultimate dissipation of energy. Studies of the data from the Kuroshio Extension have suggested that the strength of the Kuroshio is affected as it flows across the Emperor Seamounts. In the summer of 1982, a joint PMEL/-University of Washington cruise was carried out in the vicinity of the seamounts. West of these mounts (167°E) the Kuroshio was well developed, and its volume transport was $25 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (relative to 1500 db). Comparison of this transport with estimates far to the west (152°E) suggests an eastward decrease of near-surface transport ($1 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ per degree of longitude). The distribution of temperature at 300 m is a good measure of the cross-stream structure of the Kuroshio (fig. 29). The temperature gradient is proportional to the geostrophic velocity shear at 300 m. The data show that the current broadens and weakens over the seamounts and then reintensifies east of the seamounts. A similar pattern was seen in a previous study of the Kuroshio as it flows over the Izu-Ogasawara Ridge (140°E). It is suggested that this may be a characteristic response of deep oceanic jets to topography, and thus, that it could be used to evaluate the dynamical studies of topographic influences. A surprising result was the occurrence to the north of the Kuroshio of a second jet whose transport was $20 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The presence of the second jet raises the questions whether the Kuroshio branches west of the Emperor Seamounts, or whether there is a separate current which can be related to the wind field.

PLANS

- Deep-Sea Physics investigators will continue with field measurements in the EPOCS program to study the circulation in the eastern equatorial Pacific east of the Galapagos Islands (90°W). A zonal array of current meter moorings and sea-level gauges will be maintained at the Equator to study east-

Figure 28 Plots of salinity against potential density through anomalous water mass measured in Local Dynamics Experiment. Dashed lines show 2σ envelopes of salinity at a given density for entire experiment. The salinity scale is offset by 0.5 ppt for sequential profiles.

Figure 29 Distribution of temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at 300 m. The Emperor Seamounts are indicated by shading of depths less than 4000 m. Dots indicate locations of observations.

west propagation of thermocline displacements and sea surface temperature anomalies.

- Central Pacific (NORPAX) and eastern Pacific (EPOCS) hydrographic (CTD) data will be used together to study the large-scale geostrophic meridional heat flux and its relation to changes in equatorial heat content.

- At the conclusion of FY-1983, the regional study of the circulation off the west coast of South America will be complete. Planning for a major study within EPOCS of the response of the currents in the central Pacific to changes in atmospheric forcing will be done by Deep-Sea Physics scientists in conjunction with other NOAA and academic scientists.

- Analysis of CTD data from the Emperor Seamounts cruise will be carried out. The changes in structure of the currents and fronts will be described, and the processes involved will be evaluated.

THEORETICAL STUDIES

RUDOLPH W. PREISENDORFER

The Theoretical Studies Group makes use of analytical and numerical models to formulate and verify theories of physical processes in the marine environment. This work is applicable to solving problems in climate dynamics, sea-air interaction, circulation, wave propagation, and bottom boundary layer processes.

Figures 30, 31 For the present study the U.S. Mainland was divided into the 10 climate regions shown. The combined forecast skill scores of the four human forecasters (see text) were used to rank these regions in the sense of temperature and precipitation predictability (high combined scores meant high predictability and high rank). The top three predictability regions are marked with + signs, the bottom three in the ranking are marked with - signs. The four unmarked regions fall between the top and bottom of the ranking. Observe that the highest rankings occur in the west and north of the U.S. Mainland, while the lowest three are in the south and east. In each region, the number of stations at which the scores were found is shown in parentheses.

CLIMATE PREDICTABILITY

VERIFICATION OF CLIMATE PREDICTABILITY

The climate predictability project at PMEL in cooperation with the Climate Research Group (CRG) of Scripps Institution of Oceanography (which supplied the data) has made a detailed examination of an eight-year record (December 1973-February 1982, 33 seasons in all) of seasonal temperature and precipitation forecasts over the U.S. mainland. This was an unprecedented study in forecast verification in the following sense: for the eight-year period, *four distinct parallel efforts* produced forecasts each season over the U.S. mainland. The forecasts were all made in the same mode, namely terciled maps indicating above-normal, normal, and below-normal temperature and precipitation forecasts. Furthermore, the forecasts were made for the same set of seasons over the same 99-point set. The forecasters were J. Namias of CRG, Scripps; the National Weather Service (D. Gilman and three colleagues); the so-called Analoger (alias T. Barnett of Scripps and R. Preisendorfer of PMEL); and A. Douglas of the Atmospheric Science Department, Creighton University, Omaha, Nebraska.

A record was kept of each forecast map and each observed map. There were 33 such comparisons possible for each forecaster for temperature and for precipitation. These forecast/observed pairs (about 264 in all) were then compared and skill scores compiled for each forecaster. From these records were also derived the predictability of temperature and precipitation over the U.S. inland by combining the forecasters' prediction scores. [A detailed account "Climate Forecast Verifications, U.S. Mainland 1974-82" (NOAA technical memorandum, ERL PMEL-36), will be republished in condensed form.] One salient set of results is the following: (1) *Temperature* over the U.S. Mainland, as a function of season or of region, was better predicted than precipitation. (2) It was on average easier to predict temperature and precipitation in winter than in summer. (3) *Temperature* was better predicted, as a rule, for the Pacific Coast, Southwestern Desert, and Northern Plains areas, and was less well

predicted for the Southern Plains, Gulf coast, and the Atlantic Coast (see fig. 30; the numbers in parentheses give the number of stations in the region at which the scores were found). (4) *Precipitation* was better predicted, as a rule, for the Southwestern Desert, Great Northern Basin, and the Great Lakes, and was less well predicted in the Atlantic Coast (see fig. 31). In addition to evaluating the work of the four human forecaster efforts (defined above) the efforts of various nonhuman forecasters were evaluated (such as the Most Probable Markover, and the Best Analog). It was found that the forecast skills of these were competitive with those of the human forecasters. Further study of these nonhuman forecasters is planned.

HEAT AND MOMENTUM TRANSPORT

ELECTROMAGNETIC TRANSPORT MEASUREMENTS OF THE FLORIDA CURRENT

In 1982, NOAA began a program called the Subtropical Atlantic Climate Study (STACS) for studying the transport of equatorial heat to higher latitudes in the Atlantic. The initial phase of this program concentrates on measuring the transport of the Florida Current. At PMEL the transport is being estimated from the cross-stream voltage difference using a submarine cable that spans the Florida Current.

Faraday reported in 1832 on his discovery that conductors moving through a magnetic field produce electromagnetic fields, and he suggested that the Gulf Stream would produce a measureable signal. These ideas were refined by British mathematician Longuet-Higgins (1949) and applied to the Florida Current from 1952 to 1961 by Henry Stommel using a submarine cable connecting Key West, Florida, to Havana, Cuba (fig. 32), and from 1969 to 1974 by Tom Sanford using a submarine cable connecting Jupiter Inlet, Florida, to Settlement Point, Grand Bahama Island (fig. 32).

Cross-stream voltage differences reveal large annual and interannual variations caused by the Florida Current (fig.

33). The annual variation occurs mainly during the summer and fall with a fairly constant winter and spring value that is followed by a 13% increase to the summer maximum and then a 20% decrease to the fall minimum. The interannual variation (total variation minus annual variation) often exceeds the annual variation and for the present data has a maximum excursion of 30% occurring at the end of 1972.

The electromagnetic field project, which is part of STACS, began in 1982 and resumes measurements of the voltage difference across the Florida Current using the same submarine cable connecting Jupiter Inlet to Settlement Point. An inland

electric-field-sensing site was also installed at C-18 (fig. 32), and a magnetic-field-sensing site was installed at Jupiter Inlet. The measurements from these sites are being collected and will be compared with the direct measurements of the Florida Current which are being provided by current meter moorings and current profiling.

The conversion of electromagnetic data to water volume transport data requires special attention to geomagnetic noise and leakage electric current. Geomagnetic noise, induced by ionospheric and magnetospheric variations in the earlier data, can be removed by using the north magnetic

component from both San Juan, Puerto Rico, and Fredericksburg, Virginia. The results from removing the geomagnetic noise using these distant sites are given in figure 34 and are equivalent to using local magnetic data.

Leakage electric currents, electric currents that flow from water currents (in this case, the Florida Current) into the earth because the earth is not an insulator, are studied because (1) they reduce the cross-stream voltage difference from its maximum value, which is set by the volume transport, and (2) they provide an independent means of observing the time variations in Florida Current. The strength and

Figure 32 Submarine cable connects Jupiter, Florida, to Settlement Point, G.B.I.; inland electric-field-sensing site is at C-18, and magnetometer is at Jupiter. Dashed line is approximate location of the axis of the Florida Current. Note that the bottom contours are parallel to the current axis for the Jupiter region; this minimizes meandering effects of the Florida Current.

Figure 33 Cross-stream voltage differences using 5.3 years of cable data connecting Jupiter, Florida to Settlement Point, G.B.I. Top curve is daily mean values and the second curve from the top is the low-passed series with highest frequency of 4.01 cpy. The third curve is the ensemble average annual variation which is repeated for the entire series and the bottom curve is equal to the second curve minus the third. Volume transport increases toward north for increasing values of voltage. Note the summer maximum in the annual variation and the peak values in the interannual variation for 1969, 1970 and 1972.

Figure 34 The top curve is geomagnetic noise as derived from reference stations. The middle curve is the oceanographic signal which is the cable data minus the geomagnetic noise. The bottom curve is the oceanic signal minus the tides.

distribution of the leakage electric currents are influenced by the distribution of electrical conductivity beneath the Florida Current, by the width of the stream, by the spatial variations of velocity within the stream, and by the position of the stream with respect to the coastline and bottom topography.

COASTAL WAVES WAVE MODELS

As ocean waves shoal and meet an opposing current they transform from mild waves offshore into hazardous waves at coastal sites such as the Columbia River mouth, where NOAA must forecast wave conditions. These hazardous waves are usually steep and near breaking. A complete treatment of very steep (nonlinear) waves in a complex geographical location with currents is beyond the scope of all present research endeavors. In FY-1982, we began a simplified theoretical study of nonlinear wave shoaling and wave-current interaction.

The purpose of the research is to determine where shoaling and current-induced wave breaking will occur and what the wave height will be. The basic idea of the simplified, theoretical model is to approximate waves on a spatially variable current by periodic waves propagating into an opposing current which increases in time. Wave shoaling is modeled by a rising bottom. Since the theoretical model of the flow is spatially periodic only one wavelength need be considered. In fully nonlinear numerical experiments, the waves can grow to breaking. In the past year we have derived the basic equations for mass, momentum, and energy conservation in the system. Analytical work has concentrated on the shoaling problem for small-amplitude waves, and

solutions have been sought for various limiting cases. The linearized solutions will provide a framework in which to interpret the nonlinear numerical experiments.

PARTICULATE TRANSPORT PROCESSES

TIDES AND TIDAL CURRENTS

In estuaries, toxic substances are associated with particles which are themselves suspended and transported by currents. The dominant oscillating current at many sites is tidal; similarly, nonlinear, residual tidal currents often contribute to the mean current. In FY-1982, work began on a numerical model of vertically integrated, horizontal tidal currents in Puget Sound, our case-study estuary. The tidal model is a first step toward a regional model of the flux of particulate-borne pollutants in estuaries. This work is part of NOAA's Office of Marine Pollution Assessment Section 202 Long-Range Effects Research Program.

EROSION AND DEPOSITION OF FINE PARTICLES

Theoretical studies have also focused this past year on erosion and deposition in estuaries of fine particles in the bottom boundary layer, i.e., the near-bottom waters and the top layer of the bed. Fine particulates are under study because particles scavenge, and sediments store, a host of man-made contaminants. Erosion and deposition are studied because they are the least understood of a number of factors which determine the distributions of fine, bottom, con-

Figure 35 Differences in tidal velocity through the water column for cases of time-invariant (dashed line) and time-varying eddy viscosity (solid line). Effects of time-varying viscosity are most pronounced in the boundary layer ($z > \delta$); maximum bottom stress increases by 60% and higher harmonics of the fundamental motion are introduced.

taminated particulates in estuarine environments.

The amount of material suspended by a flow is determined by the magnitude of stress that flow exerts on the bottom. Accurate characterization of the bottom stress and the strength of the eddy diffusivity which distributes the sediment in the water column is therefore essential to modeling the fate of some pollutants. During the past year, models have been developed which take into account the interaction

of tidal flow and time-varying turbulence (fig. 35). These show that the neglect of the time-varying aspect of turbulence results in underestimates of bottom stress at maximum stress and distortion of the flow profile near times of flow reversal. More importantly, the basic model identifies the dependence of bottom friction on velocity, which is important to vertically integrated tidal-flow models. In addition, the theory permits the evaluation of the magnitude of the related friction coefficients.

Local, fine-particle erosion/deposition was modeled as a time-dependent advection-diffusion process, where the material source at the boundary has a strength and time-dependence linked to the flow by the bottom stress. These models have been compared with data from three tidal environments with favorable results. Comparisons of this kind lead to knowledge of the distributions of settling velocities of the resuspended material and to estimates of the in situ erosion rates for tidally resuspended fine sediment. Both results are required before regional redistribution of contaminated particles in estuaries can be addressed. The work here has been undertaken in conjunction with investigators from the Coastal Physics and Geochemistry groups.

PLANS

- Remove the geomagnetic noise from the cable and inland electric-field site data and construct realistic numerical electromagnetic models for assessing the magnitude of time variations in the electromagnetic transport data caused by time variations in the position and internal structure of the Florida Current. The models will be verified by comparison

with direct observations of volume transport and with inland electric-field site data.

- Study of wave shoaling with complex bathymetry and adverse currents by simplifying the problem and considering only small-amplitude (linear) waves. In FY-1983 plans are to construct a model of linear wave-current-bathymetry interaction at the Columbia River mouth, a site of hazardous waves.

- The numerical model of tides in Puget Sound is scheduled for completion in FY-1983. Plans are to couple this with a model of sediment erosion and deposition in the bottom boundary layer.

- Evaluate erosion and deposition rates for fine sediment subject to tidal flow at a second site in Puget Sound, and initiate the development of horizontal transport models incorporating those results.

The historical sea surface temperature (HSST) set, which is a compendium of world-ocean temperature, wind, and other variables starting about 1860, will be examined for interdecadal changes in global SST anomaly patterns. Because the HSST is an agglomerate of data collected under widely different conditions, a large part of the initial examination will be for data integrity, and information content. The verifiability and falsifiability of physical hypotheses reached by future studies of the HSST will be strongly dependent on its integrity and information content.

MARINE METEOROLOGICAL STUDIES

JAMES E. OVERLAND

The Marine Meteorological Studies Group examines coastal winds and waves and sea-ice processes by means of a combination of field measurements, remote-sensing techniques, and numerical modeling. The group's purpose is to improve meteorological forecasts by conducting descriptive studies and providing interpretive models to operational components of NOAA. Studies of sea-ice processes are also applicable to NOAA's climate research.

Figure 36 Anemometer mast deployed in the Southern Bering Sea in February 1981 to measure the interaction between wind and ice.

SEA ICE PROCESSES

ICE DYNAMICS

During 1981, PMEL sponsored a February-March cruise aboard the NOAA ship *Surveyor* along the Bering Sea ice edge to study the ice structure and its response to oceanographic and meteorological forcing. This study was carried out in conjunction with researchers from the Department of Oceanography and the Polar Science Center at the University of Washington, the Scott Polar Research Institute in England, and NASA.

The 1981 experiment investigated and successfully recorded the effects of storms on the marginal ice zone. Swell generated by a storm with southerly wind fields broke up the floes more than 100 km into the pack and contributed to roughening the surfaces. Ice stations and ARGOS position buoys were deployed after the storm passed. The experiment produced a 64-hour time series of ice drift, wind velocity, and relative current for a floe in the inner marginal ice zone

Figure 37 The NOAA WP-3D research aircraft in Anchorage, Alaska, February 1982. This aircraft measures wind, temperature, heat and momentum fluxes, and sea ice properties with a variety of onboard sensors.

(MIZ) and an eight-day record of ice drift at three stations. The ice velocities during the experiment were among the largest ever measured for sea ice (0.5 m s^{-1}). During 1982, analysis of these data produced a number of results with important implications for ice modeling. Ice drift was influenced by the tides on this shallow shelf; floes were advected by the tidal current and accelerated by the sea surface tilt due to the slope of tidal height. The ratio of atmospheric drag coefficient to oceanic drag coefficient calculated from the relative wind and current velocities was similar to ratios determined for Arctic ice. The magnitude of atmospheric drag coefficient, calculated from 168 twenty-minute samples of velocity measured at four levels on a meteorological tower (fig. 36) were among the largest observed for pack ice, 3.1×10^{-3} for a 10-m reference level. We attribute the large ice velocities to the validity of the free-drift assumption (i.e., 95% of the force balance is accounted for by wind stress and current drag), so the effect of the aerodynamic roughness of the broken ice is large.

In February 1982, with the aid of the Office of Naval Research, PMEL completed the BERING-82 experiment, a study of ice drift and thermodynamics in the central Bering Sea. For the experiment, an array of two meteorological/oceanographic ice stations and six ARGOS buoys were deployed from Nome by helicopter and a total of five research flights were made by NOAA WP-3D aircraft from Anchorage (fig. 37). The intent of the experiment was to provide research support in the Bering to the Navy-NOAA Joint Ice Center and the Alaska Region of the National Weather Service as part of the marine observation and prediction program.

The ice stations oscillated north and south through the Bering Strait (fig. 38) in response to wind and current. This result is of critical importance because it shows that some Arctic sea ice is actually produced in the Bering Sea. The aircraft experiment also documented the types of ice in the ice growth regions, the central Bering Sea, and the ice edge (fig. 39).

Results of this research have been incorporated into a sea ice prediction model for the Bering Sea which calculates the balance between advection by wind and the growth and melting of the ice.

GOES ENVIRONMENTAL MONITOR (GEM)

An important aspect of both the Puget Sound Wind Study and Bering Sea experiments has been the development of a data collection platform (GEM-GOES Environmental Monitor), which transmits data through the GOES (Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite) satellite. This development was particularly important for sea ice studies because the cost of ships and helicopters for deployment is often more than the cost of the platforms. In the BERING-82

experiment two ice stations were deployed (fig. 40a and b) which reported wind, current, air and sea temperature, floe rotation, and position. The expendable nature of these platforms allowed for the long time series shown in figure 38. The collection system also permits scientific analysis to begin shortly after data collection by providing the appropriate computer program library.

PMEL has been a leader in the development of these technologies, and we now consider their development to be complete for the needs of our program.

COASTAL WINDS AND WAVES HAZARDOUS COASTAL WAVES

The waves project provides improved wave-forecasting techniques to the National Weather Service, particularly for major river entrances and other hazardous coastal areas. Analysis is proceeding on a unique data set collected at the Columbia River entrance, one of the most dangerous navigation regions in the world. Results indicate that (a) refraction by currents is the primary physical mechanism responsible for wave amplification on the bar; (b) in terms of significant wave height (H_s), the wave-height amplification can exceed 40% for a peak ebb current of 2 m s^{-1} (4 kn); and (c) there is agreement between published tidal-current prediction tables and subsurface observations (at 7-m depth) at a mid-channel location 5 miles from the river entrance; however, surface currents at the entrance can exceed predicted up-river values by 20%.

Figure 41 is an example of the Columbia River observations collected within 30 minutes of the predicted time of peak ebb current on September 11, 1981, in cooperation with the National Ocean Survey (NOS). The image itself is from a side-looking airborne radar (SLAR) collected by aircraft of the Oregon Army National Guard. The two arrows near the entrance indicate surface current estimates of 2 m s^{-1} , derived from surface drifters tracked by shore-based radar; the corresponding prediction for a point two miles up-river was 1.6 meters per second. The “+” signs indicate

the locations of the Waverider deployments which provided significant wave height estimates; these increase from 1.5 to 3.6 m approaching the entrance. On the basis of these data, we assume that H_s at the entrance was in excess of 4 m. The offshore significant wave height was 2.9 m, as measured by a NOAA buoy (not shown), which indicates that the wave amplification on the bar was in excess of 40%. The imagery illustrates that wave refraction by currents is the primary physical mechanism responsible for the focusing of wave energy at the entrance. Close examination of the image shows that refraction is so severe that crossing of wave crests occurs in the entrance. This extreme refraction, however, is not evident on similar SLAR imagery (not shown) taken during the previous slack period when offshore wave conditions were nearly identical.

HAZARDOUS WINDS

Results from the Puget Sound Wind Study, completed in 1981, were transferred to the National Weather Service (NWS). In addition, four seminars with NWS forecasters were conducted by PMEL and University of Washington (UW) researchers to discuss applications of recent research to Puget Sound forecasting. A guide to the marine weather of Western Washington, which incorporated recent research results, was produced. In addition, for the inland waters of Western Washington, a set of composite surface wind and wind persistence field representations was assembled that are keyed to the wind direction measured at 850 mb by an atmospheric balloon sounding on the coast at Quillayute, Washington. The 850-mb wind is used as an indicator of the large-scale weather pattern. The composite fields show that the wind directions in the sea-level channels of the region vary in a regular fashion as the large-scale weather varies. These maps were given to NWS forecasters as an aid to improving predictions of marine winds in Puget Sound.

A significant barrier to the further improvement in forecast capability for the Puget Sound region is the lack of a local data synthesis and display capability. To explore various approaches, PMEL sponsored a workshop on data assimilation which included participants representing NWS,

Figure 38. Partial track of ice buoys through the Bering Strait during the 1982 experiment. The track illustrates the interaction of the ice in the Bering and Chukchi Seas to the north.

Figure 40a Meteorological station deployed in the Bering Sea in February 1982. The current meter and water temperature sensor are attached to an aluminum pipe which extends below the electronics box on the left.

Figure 39a Ice formation in Bristol Bay, Alaska. This feature is called "grease ice." The wind speed is 15 m s^{-1} and the air temperature is -15°C .

Figure 39b This ice is typical of the central Bering Sea with floe sizes of 50m.

Figure 39c This figure shows ice floes melting in the warm ocean water near the ice edge. The ice often forms in features called bands.

Figure 40b Meteorological and oceanographic data collected by station 5170 from 1-8 February 1982. Ocean data are shown by the dashed lines and meteorological data by solid lines. Current speed is in cm s^{-1} ; current direction is the vector direction. Wind speed is in m s^{-1} ; wind direction is in the meteorological sense, the direction from which the wind comes. Meteorological measurements are taken 3 m above the ice and oceanographic measurements are approximately 2 m below the ice bottom. This figure was produced two months after data collection.

Figure 41 Example of Columbia River observations.

PMEL, UW, Atmospheric Environmental Service, Vancouver, B.C., and the ERL PROFS (Prototype Regional Observation and Forecasting System) Program. Discussions centered on availability of data sources for real-time display and approaches for operational implementation. As a result of this workshop, the University of Washington, in cooperation with NWS, is designing a data collection and processing system for analysis and forecasting in the Puget Sound region.

PLANS

- PMEL will deliver and evaluate forecast products of the National Weather Service for sea ice in the Bering Sea and for hazardous waves at the Columbia River entrance.
- We will improve our capability to process large meteorological and sea ice data sets and begin study of large-scale air-sea-ice interaction, important to climate and long-range weather prediction.
- The Marine Meteorological Studies Group and the Coastal Physics Group will participate in the Marginal Ice Zone Experiment in the Bering Sea (MIZEX-WEST) during February 1983. The experiment involves measurements taken from the ice breaker *Westwind* and the NOAA Ship *Discoverer* and aircraft measurements from the NOAA WP-3D and the NASA CV990 research aircraft. Data will be used to evaluate the sea ice forecasting model and document regional sea ice physics in the Bering Sea.

ENGINEERING STUDIES

HUGH B. MILBURN

The Engineering Studies Group is a multidisciplinary activity which supports Laboratory research through project engineering. The Group is responsive to the needs of a broad range of investigators, and the nature and scope of projects vary accordingly. Support is provided in the fields of electronics, mechanics, materials, and software engineering, with emphasis on expanding and refining our capability to make accurate measurements in the marine environment.

HEAT AND MOMENTUM TRANSPORT

FREE-FALL VELOCITY/CTD PROFILER

The free-fall profiler, called TOPS, was used on two cruises in the EPOCS area (eastern equatorial Pacific). The profiler collects relative velocity data with an onboard acoustic velocimeter. Conductivity, temperature, and depth information are recorded internally and the motions of the profiler body are monitored with a 2-axis accelerometer and a flux-gate magnetometer. A hydrodynamic model which describes the response of the vehicle to the ocean shear flow was developed and used to interpret TOPS data. The model combines the vehicle motion and the measured relative velocity to yield the actual water velocity (relative to an arbitrary offset). When TOPS is tracked in a net of bottom-moored transponders, absolute position and velocity are computed from acoustic travel times. This velocity is compared with the model results as shown in figure 42. During one cruise, drops were made concurrently with the release of an Expendable Current Profiler, which works on the principles of geomagnetic induction to measure water velocity. This data is also shown in the figure. The close agreement of these three independent methods of measuring water velocity adds confidence to the techniques employed.

ELECTRIC FIELD DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM

A prototype electric field data acquisition system was installed on the east Florida coast near Jupiter, Florida, in support of the STACS program. The recording system is connected to two pairs of silver/silver chloride electrodes placed in the water near the shoreline and separated by 800 m. The small electric potential that is observed is a function of the volume transport of the Florida current which, at the Jupiter site, flows essentially parallel to the shore. A high-resolution, flux-gate magnetometer was also installed in the vicinity to monitor the changes in the Earth's magnetic field that

cause variations in the induced electric currents. In addition, recorders were placed on the ends of a submarine cable that spans the Florida Current from Jupiter to the Grand Bahama Island. These cross-stream voltage differences provide another indirect measure of variations in the volume transport. Severe lightning storms caused serious failures of the electric field and magnetometer systems at the beginning of the field experiment, but elaborate protection devices have since been installed and have greatly reduced the vulnerability of the electronics to lightning damage.

THERMISTOR CHAIN

A low-cost buoy system to monitor ocean temperature was developed and deployed in the EPOCS area as shown schematically in figure 43. Engineering design work began in the late fall of 1981, and the prototype buoy was moored on station in March 1982. The system is capable of measuring air and sea temperatures to 500 m and then telemetering the data ashore via the ARGOS satellite. (Data is also redundantly recorded in this prototype on an internal recorder.) The satellite data collection scheme is economical in terms of hardware acquisition costs and in the sense that data can be recovered regardless of the fate of the mooring.

In the past, the sea cable that brings data from the mooring line aboard the surface buoy has been the most difficult aspect of this type of project. We have designed a robust, double-armoured cable and heavily encased it in a tapered, polyurethane strain-relief boot which protects the internal electrical conductors from mechanical fatigue. The temperature sensors along the cable contain active components that send timed multiplex data up the line on command from the buoy electronics. Pressure along the cable is also measured to allow the catenary of the mooring to be determined. Although the telemetry unit suffered an early failure, this first deployment will be useful in evaluating the basic design of the system components.

Figure 43 ARGOS telemetering temperature buoy.

FLUID/PARTICLE TRANSPORT PROCESSES

AUTOMATED FREON ANALYZER

A system to strip freon from discrete water samples taken at sea was designed and fabricated. A commercial microprocessor based controller was combined with a series of valves and temperature controllers to strip and prepare samples for injection to a gas chromatograph (fig. 44).

This semiautomatic mode of laboratory analysis greatly reduced the work load of the chromatographer and assures uniformity in the handling of replicate samples. The system was proven operational during the CO₂ cruise in the western Pacific and has been used extensively in laboratory saturation studies. Other trace-gas sampling systems will incorporate the techniques and hardware developed for the freon system, and further automation will expand the capabilities of the researchers at sea.

Figure 44 a. Freon stripper board (front). b. Freon stripper board (back).

SEDIMENT TRAP EFFICIENCY

An effort to determine the collection efficiency of the recently developed Sequentially Sampling Sediment Trap (S^sT) was carried out in the main basin of Puget Sound. Several configurations of the traps were deployed on subsurface moorings along with current meters and transmissometers. The effects of changing the aspect ratio (i.e., the height-to-diameter ratio) was investigated, and a ratio of approximately 3:1 was determined optimum for the 26-cm diameter cylinders. Diver inspection of traps that had been on station for several weeks revealed a biological fouling problem that was readily corrected and also led to a change in the funnel design. Although it is yet unrealistic to assume the traps yield true vertical flux values, we are now confident the sampling scheme produces repeatable data. It will be further tested in 1983.

AESOPS

The 200-kHz Acoustic Echosounding and Profiling System (AESOPS) was made operational through many refinements to the transceiver and underwater unit. Test cruises have demonstrated the system's portability and reliability, and it can now be used in ongoing and future projects. Software has been developed under contract to digitize and enhance the return signal. Coefficients for beam corrections, time variable gain, attenuation, and other factors are considered in the programs that develop volume backscatter values. Although often overlooked or disregarded, post-processing is an important element of acoustic remote sensing and will soon be a routine product of the AESOPS efforts.

TSUNAMI

Two pressure gauges have been deployed in the eastern Pacific in anticipation of attaining the signature of the passing tsunami. One gauge is in 16 meters of water on the east side of San Cristobal Island in the Galapagos Archipelago. The gauge is collocated with one of four gauges placed in the EPOCS sea-level variation study area. The other tsunami gauge is on the Equator at 95°W at a depth of 3800 m. Both gauges utilize a Paros Scientific Digiquartz pressure gauge and sample approximately once per minute. The expected sensitivity of the deep gauge is less than 90 Pa, which will allow the observance of a 1-cm-high wave. Present laboratory and field efforts are directed at determining the actual response characteristics of these high-pressure gauges.

PLANS

- A second temperature buoy will be fabricated and deployed in the EPOCS area.
- Electric field and magnetometer recorders will be maintained and upgraded in support of the STACS project.
- A vector-averaging ARGOS telemetering wind recorder will be fabricated and deployed in the tropical Pacific.
- A semiautomatic N₂O stripper system will be fabricated to facilitate shipboard trace-gas analysis.

FACILITIES

The PMEL staff and research facilities occupy leased space at three sites. The Showboat Apartments on the University of Washington campus house the office of the Director and senior scientific and support staff of the Theoretical Studies, Deep-Sea Physics, Marine Meteorological Studies, and Coastal Physics groups. At Sand Point, the Tower Building is occupied by Technical and Administrative Support and support staff for the Coastal Physics Group. Hangar 32 at Sand Point is the location of the Geochemistry Group, Engineering Studies Group, and support staff for the Coastal and Deep-Sea Physics groups. The Seattle-based staff and facilities are to be consolidated in Research Building 1 at the Western Regional Center when it is completed in 1983.

COMPUTER FACILITIES

The computer facilities based at the Showboat Apartments consist of a remote job entry (RJE) station and a satellite-image-processing system. A large portion of PMEL's investigators rely on the RJE operations to quickly receive the results of their data analysis, data reduction, modeling, and graphic display programs. The image-processing system enables investigators to manipulate and display previously collected satellite data.

PMEL's RJE facility has a Calcomp 1051, 36-inch drum plotter with 4-pen capability, as well as a Unitech system that incorporates an operator's console, a card reader, tape drive, line printer, and NOVA microcomputer. The RJE is linked by leased telephone line to NOAA's Cyber 170/750 computer in Boulder, Colorado. Users accessing the Cyber by terminal or through the RJE card reader can have their job output listed on the RJE line printer, and plot files can be spooled at the RJE's tape drive. There is no job execution or tape file processing performed directly on the RJE equipment. For terminal users, a statistical multiplexer permits a number of hard-wired and dial-up communications lines through the RJE telephone line.

LIBRARY

The Charnell-Laird Memorial Library at PMEL, operated by EDIS, is housed in temporary quarters at the Tower Building. The collection now holds more than 2000 volumes and subscribes to more than 125 journals. A computer terminal provides the capability of searching more than 200 bibliographic data bases from such systems as DIALOG, Bibliographic Retrieval Services, *New York Times* Information Service, Legislate-Regulate, Chemical Substances Information Network, Institute for Scientific Information, and Chemical Information System.

A periodicals reading area is maintained at the Showboat where current journals are available for browsing. Back issues of journals are archived on microfilm as a means of saving space and can be viewed using the library's reader-printer.

Holdings are cataloged on-line, using the OCLC system. Records in the NOAA Union Catalog can be accessed by all NOAA libraries, and the holdings of other NOAA libraries are also available to PMEL staff through the same Union Catalog.

GRAPHICS

PMEL's graphics section, composed of a photographic staff and an illustration and drafting staff, provides illustration for the Laboratory's research results.

The photo-lab personnel provide specialized scientific services including contrast enhancement, multispectral false color, digital false color, mosaic, and composite photographs, in addition to general photographic services such as black-and-white and color slides from original art, photo-mechanical transfer (PMT) copies of line originals, precision enlargements and reductions, field documentation, photo copies of continuous-tone material, and duplicate slides.

The illustration and drafting staff is responsible for illustrations, graphs, maps, charts, mechanical drawings, bro-

chures, and visual presentations and displays for papers and presentations by PMEL authors.

PUBLICATIONS

Publications of research data and analysis papers at professional conferences, in professional journals and bulletins, and as NOAA reports and memoranda is the culmination of the gathering of scientific information for PMEL scientists. The PMEL publications list for FY-1982 includes 80 titles.

In the publications section, manuscripts are entered into the word-processing system, proofread, and when appropriate, edited and assembled with graphics or photographic illustrations in preparation for publication. Recently, the preparation of camera-ready copy for journals, as well as ERL publications, has also been done on a limited basis. Other services include production work on the PMEL Annual Report, mailing lists and labels for mass mailings, and distribution of some PMEL publications. PMEL has three IBM OS/6 keyboards for recording material on diskettes and two high-speed, ink-jet printers.

ENGINEERING AND ELECTRONICS

The primary capabilities for engineering development within PMEL reside in the Engineering Studies Group. Developmental work is undertaken in response to specific project needs, and close communication is maintained between engineers and scientists during the design and fabrication of unique marine instrumentation.

A major effort in the group has been directed toward the application of microprocessor technology for data collection, processing, and storage. The development process is aided

with extensive support equipment, including a microcomputer, which supports a cross-assembler for the development and testing of system software. The computer is also linked with cassette tape readers to provide a reliable and versatile data-tape translation facility.

GEOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS

A variety of diverse instrumentation for the acquisition and analysis of samples from estuarine and oceanic environments is held by the Geochemistry Group. In addition to conventional apparatus for sample collection from the water and sediment columns (e.g., Niskin bottles of various types and sizes, filtration systems, bottom grab samplers, gravity and box corers), a collection of state-of-the-art equipment has been acquired by the group.

For trace metal studies, an ultra-clean sampling system consisting of a Kevlar cable-winch system, Teflon messengers, and Teflon coatings on all sample contact surfaces, a portable "clean van" capable of providing a sequestered, Class-100, sample-processing environment aboard ship, and several portable, laminar-flow hoods are available. To ensure contamination-free collection of ultra-low-level trace gases dissolved in seawater (e.g., the Freons), a glass syringe-sampler has been designed and adapted for use with standard rosettes. A submersible pump and high-speed centrifuge system (configured with a continuous-flow head) is utilized to collect gram quantities of suspended matter from estuarine waters for organic geochemical analysis. The centrifuge has been tested for shipboard use in sea conditions. Sequentially sampling sediment traps have been developed at

PMEL for studies of the flux and composition of vertically settling suspended matter. Up to ten samples can be collected with a single sediment trap, thus providing information regarding the temporal variability in flux density and particle composition. Suspended matter distribution and transport studies are furthered by the use of beam transmissometers that can be mounted on moored arrays for acquisition of time series data or linked with a CTD system for in-situ and continuous water-column profiling. Interstitial water in marine sediments can be sampled in situ for trace gases and some trace metals with a gas harpoon developed by PMEL.

The geochemistry laboratories are equipped with Class-100, contamination-free work spaces, inert-atmosphere work spaces, a cold laboratory, electronic microbalances, ultrasonic dispersers, refrigerated centrifuges, particle-free water delivery systems, and the usual collection of analytical balances, pH meters, ovens, freezers, and so on.

A broad base of analytical instrumentation is used to support geochemical research both aboard ship and in the laboratory. Included in the collection of instruments are two gas chromatograph mass spectrometers (Hewlett-Packard 5991 and 5993), four Hewlett-Packard gas chromatographs equipped with electron capture and flame ionization detectors (normally interfaced with helium purge-and-trap water sample "strippers"* or atmospheric samplers* for methane, carbon monoxide, nitrous oxide, Freons, etc.), a Perkin Elmer high-pressure liquid chromatograph, two carbon and nitrogen analyzers (Perkin Elmer 240B and Hewlett-Packard 185B), a Kevex 0700-7077 energy dispersive X-ray spectrometer, two heated, graphite atomization-equipped, atomic-absorption spectrophotometers (Perkin Elmer 603-HGA500-AS40 and 305A-HGA2000), a Perkin Elmer 554,

scanning, visible-ultraviolet spectrophotometer, a radioanalytical counting system (an Ortec 576 silicon, surface barrier alpha detector, and a Gamma Products sodium iodide crystal gamma detector linked with a Tracor Northern 1710 multi-channel analyzer), a Metrohm 636 titroprocessor, an ISI MINI-SEM II scanning electron microscope, an electron column coupled Kevex 5100 energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometer, a particle-size analysis system* (Coulter ZBI Analyzer Channelizer and Log Expander, and Hewlett-Packard 9825A controller), and a Dupont-Sorvall density-gradient ultracentrifuge system.

DIVING UNIT

The diving unit established in FY-1979 continues to accommodate the diving needs of several of the Laboratory projects. Several current meter and sediment trap moorings are periodically serviced by divers. As part of EPOCS, PMEL is maintaining pressure-temperature gauges (PTG) in the Galápagos Islands, and divers are replacing these sensors annually.

Since diver proficiency is vital to a safe diving program PMEL divers have participated in advanced NOAA-sponsored training and made frequent working dives to inspect and clean current meters and other equipment. PMEL presently has five NOAA-certified scuba divers.

*Effective shipboard use demonstrated.

COOPERATIVE INSTITUTES

Fiscal year 1982 was the fifth year of PMEL's involvement with the Joint Institute for the Study of the Atmosphere and Ocean (JISAO) at the University of Washington, and the Joint Institute for Marine and Atmospheric Research (JIMAR) at the University of Hawaii. The institutes provide a structure for research collaboration and training in areas of mutual interest to NOAA and the academic community. A series of distinguished visiting scientists is supported through the institutes each year to present seminars and interact with the institute staff and graduate students.

JISAO JOHN M. WALLACE, Director

The main areas of emphasis within the Joint Institute for the Study of Atmosphere and Ocean continue to be climate dynamics, estuarine processes, and environmental chemistry, with climate dynamics continuing to be dominant. Research in this area during FY-1982 has involved a variety of topics, including the nature and causes of sea surface temperature anomalies in the equatorial Pacific Ocean, seasonal variability in the equatorial Atlantic, studies of mesoscale oceanic eddies based on the motions of quasi-Lagrangian floats, sudden stratospheric warmings, and recurrent "weather regimes" in a simplified model of the atmospheric circulation.

Activities sponsored, fully or in part, by JISAO at the University of Washington during FY-1982 are summarized in the following tables. Short visits by scientists from other institutions and longer term visiting appointments are summarized separately, and within each table visitors are grouped by research field.

JISAO VISITING SCIENTISTS FY-1982 Short Term

Dates	Name and Affiliation	Seminar Topic
CLIMATE		
9/29 - 10/1/81	Dr. Kevin Hamilton National Center for Atmospheric Research	"One and two dimensional models of the quasi-biennial oscillation."
10/14 - 10/16/81	Dr. Melvin Shapiro National Center for Atmospheric Research	"Geostrophic, convective, and turbulent forcing of ageostrophic circulations."
11/9 - 11/11/81	Dr. Ed Schneider Harvard University	"A semi-diagnostic study of the maintenance of the zonally averaged general circulation."
11/12 - 11/14/81	Zulema Garrafo Princeton University	"Diurnal atmospheric tide in the troposphere and stratosphere."
11/22 - 11/25/81	Dr. Brian Reinhold Massachusetts Institute of Technology	"Dynamics of weather regimes: Quasistationary waves and blocking."
11/22 - 11/25/81	Dr. Brian Reinhold Massachusetts Institutes of Technology	"Dynamics of weather regimes: Quasistationary waves and blocking."
11/29 - 12/3/81	Dr. George Philander NOAA Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory	"Coastal upwelling and eastern boundary currents."
12/7 - 12/11/81	Dr. Peter J. Webster CSIRO Division of Atmospheric Physics Australia	"Seasonality in climate response with some thoughts on climate prediction."
12/13 - 12/15/81	Richard D. Romea Oregon State University	"Coastal trapped waves along the Peruvian coast."
12/15 - 12/18/81	Dr. Edward Sarachick Harvard University	"The observational evidence for ocean heat transports." "An overview of the coupled atmosphere-ocean system."
12/16 - 12/19/81	Dr. Michael J. McPhaden National Center for Atmospheric Research	"Sea surface temperature variability in the central equatorial Indian Ocean: A case study."
1/17 - 1/27/82	Dr. Thomas Rossby University of Rhode Island	(scientific discussions)
2/22 - 2/27/82	Lawrence J. Pratt Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution	"Rotating channel flow over large obstacles."

3/1/82	Dr. Yale Mintz NASA Goddard Laboratory for the Atmospheric Sciences	"Modeling the global hydrologic cycle."
3/3 - 3/7/82	Dr. George Veronis Yale University	"Determination of absolute oceanic velocities."
3/7 - 3/10/82	Qing-Cun Zeng Chinese Academy of Sciences	"On the evolution of disturbances and their interaction with the zonal mean flow."
3/29 - 4/4/82	Dr. W.S. Broecker Lamont-Doherty Geophysical Observatory	"Methods of reconstructing the preanthropogenic CO ₂ content."
4/20 - 4/25/82	Dr. Lorenz Maggaard University of Hawaii	"Rossby waves in the North Pacific"
4/27 - 4/28/82	Dr. Allan Robinson Harvard University	"A combined statistical and dynamical approach to the description and prediction of oceanic fields."
5/4 - 5/5/82	Dr. Greg Holloway Institute of Ocean Sciences, Canada	"Shoot the weatherman? Predictability of the weather."
5/4 - 5/5/82	Dr. Ann Gargett Institute of Ocean Sciences, Canada	"A parameterization of vertical diffusivity in the ocean."
5/30 - 6/2/82	Dr. Jürgen Willebrand Max-Planck Institute, Hamburg, W. Germany	"Does the beta spiral work with climatological data?"
6/16 - 6/19/82	Dr. Graeme Stevens CSIRO Division of Atmospheric Physics, Australia	"Clouds and climate."
6/16 - 6/20/82	Dr. Claes Rooth University of Miami	"Fresh water feedback in ocean circulation."
7/20/82	Dr. Greg Holloway Institute of Ocean Sciences, Canada	"Stirring and transport of tracers in geostrophic turbulence."
8/3 - 8/4/82	Dr. Randy Dole Harvard University	"Persistent anomalies of the extratropical Northern Hemisphere wintertime circulation."
8/2 - 8/7/82	Dr. Christien Colin COB/Brest, France	"Low-frequency variability in the Gulf of Guinea."
8/11 - 8/14/82	Prof. Michael Longuet-Higgins Cambridge University, England	"The skewness of sea-surface slopes."
8/31 - 9/3/82	Dr. Richard Greatbatch Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory, Princeton University	"On the response of the ocean to a moving storm: A general overview."

ESTUARINE

10/4 - 10/8/81	Dr. R. J. Uncles Institute for Marine Environmental Research, England	"Modeling of circulation and mixing in the Bristol Channel and some applications to ecosystem studies."
10/7 - 11/10/81	Dr. Keith Dyer Institute of Ocean Sciences, Taunton, England	"The consequences of lateral internal seiching in a partially mixed estuary."
11/29 - 12/2/82	Dr. Richard Thomson Institute of Ocean Sciences, Canada	"Inertial waves and shelf waves: Two dominant facets of the circulation in British Columbia's coastal waters."
7/21 - 7/30/82	Dr. D. Howell Peregrine Bristol University (visiting at Scripps)	"The Severn Bore: A descriptive account."
10/11 - 10/12/81	Dr. Henning Rodhe Stockholm University	"Secular atmospheric chemistry changes and the chemical climate of Europe."
2/17 - 2/20/82	Dr. Robert Cook University of Colorado	"Consequences of deliberate acidification of a lake."
3/9 - 3/10/82	Dr. Aslam Khalil The Oregon Graduate Center	"Long-term variations of atmospheric methane and the CH ₄ -OH-CO cycle."
4/19/82	Dr. Emmett B. Moore Batelle Northwest	"Decommissioning of nuclear facilities."
9/2 - 9/5/82	Dr. Bruce Honeyman Stanford University	"Adsorption of trace elements onto composite materials in natural aquatic systems."

POLLUTANT TRANSPORT

4/21 - 4/22/82	Dr. George Knauer Moss Landing Marine Labs	"Mn flux, residence times, and rates of change in the northeastern Pacific."
5/4 - 5/7/82	Dr. Yuan-Hui Li Lamont-Doherty Geophysical Observatory	"Removal processes for radionuclides in coastal waters." "Geochemical cycles of the elements in the ocean."
5/25 - 5/28/82	Dr. James Kirk Cochran Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution	"Natural radionuclide studies of particle mixing rates in nearshore and deep sea sediments." "Lab studies of nuclide migration in nearshore sediments."

JISAO VISITING SCIENTISTS Long Term

Dates	Name	Affiliation (previous or current)
CLIMATE (School of Oceanography)		
1/2/81 -	Dr. Stephen Riser	School of Oceanography, University of Rhode Island
8/1/81 - 7/31/82	Dr. Harry Bryden	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
6/1/82 -	Dr. Michael J. McPhaden	formerly National Center for Atmospheric Research (Department of Atmospheric Sciences)
3/1/79 - 12/31/81	Dr. Carl Youngblut	NASA Laboratory for Atmospheric Sciences, Goddard Space Flight Center
10/22/79 - 10/19/81	Dr. Alan O'Neill	British Meteorological Office
2/16/82 -	Dr. Brian B. Reinhold	Department of Meteorology, MIT
INSTITUTE SCIENTISTS		
9/1/79 -	Dr. Curtis Mobley PMEL	
10/1/79 - 9/17/82	Dr. Cho-Teng Liu PMEL	University of Taiwan Taipei, Republic of China
11/1/80 - 7/31/82	Dr. John P. Blaha PMEL	U.S. Navy Oceanographic Office Bay St. Louis, Mississippi
7/1/82 -	Peter B. Wright PMEL	

JISAO Publications List

1979

- Holloway, Greg: On the spectral evolution of strongly interacting waves. *J. Geoph. Astr. Fluid Dynamics*, 2, 271-287.
- Ripa, Pedro M.: Non-linear wave-wave interactions in the equatorial B-plane. *Ocean Modelling* (Cambridge), 22, 3-6.

1980

- Davey, Michael K.: A quasi-linear theory for rotating flow over topography, Part I: Steady B-plane channel. *J. Fluid Mech.*, 99, 297-320.
- Davey, Michael K.: A quasi-linear theory for rotating flow over topography, Part II: Beta-plane annulus. *J. Fluid Mech.*

Davey, Michael K.: Numerical calculation of the spectral representation of $\underline{u} \cdot \nabla \chi$ for doubly periodic flow. Department of Oceanography, Special Report No. 93, University of Washington, Seattle, Washington.

Davey, Michael K. and V.O. Ivchenko: Asymmetric Reynolds stress and an eddy parameterization for the area-averaged ocean circulation. *Ocean Modelling*, 33, 5-7.

Edmon, Harold J.: A study of the general circulation over the Northern Hemisphere during 1976-77 and 1977-78. *Mon. Wea. Rev.*, 108, 1538-1553.

Edmon, Harold J., B.J. Hoskins, and M.E. McIntyre: Eliassen-Palm cross sections for the troposphere. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 17, 2600-2616.

Youngblut, Carl, and T. Sasamori: The nonlinear effects of transient and stationary eddies on the winter mean circulation. Part I: Diagnostic analysis. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 37, 1944-1957.

1981

Cushman-Roisin, Benoit: Effects of horizontal advection on upper ocean mixing: A case of frontogenesis. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, 11, 1345-1356.

Cushman-Roisin, Benoit: Penetrative convection in the upper ocean due to surface cooling. *Geophys. Astrophys. Fluid Dynam.*, 19, 61-9.

Davey, Michael K., and J.A. Whitehead: Rotating Rayleigh-Taylor instability as a model of sinking events in the ocean. *J. Geophys. Astrophys. Fluid Dynam.*, 17, 237-253.

Durkerton, T., C.-P.F. Hsu, and M.E. McIntyre: Some Eulerian and Lagrangian diagnostics for a model stratospheric warming. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 38, 89-843.

Hoskins, Brian J., and David Karoly: The steady linear response of a spherical atmosphere and orographic forcing. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 38, 78-1196.

Youngblut, Carl, and T. Sasamori: The nonlinear effects of transient and stationary eddies on the winter mean circulation. Part II: The stability of stationary waves. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 38, 87-96.

JIMAR

DENNIS MOORE, Director

The principal research interests of the Joint Institute for Marine and Atmospheric Research are tsunami, equatorial oceanography, and climate. Work continues on a finite element model for tsunami propagation over irregular topography, development of a shallow-water digital tsunami gauge, and on establishing a tsunami-monitoring capability in Hawaii. A manual on post-tsunami surveys was written. A postevent survey of Hurricane Iwa will be conducted to determine whether there was a storm surge associated with the hurricane.

A series of 58 tornado events during the period 1976-1981 was examined, and it was found that 82% of the events were associated with cirrus surges over the eastern Pacific Ocean 24 hours prior to the outbreak of tornado activity. An E.O.F. analysis of Hawaiian rainfall distributions was completed. A study of secular changes in carbon dioxide concentrations at Moana Loa in relation to the atmospheric circulation was completed and published. Marine deck data was studied to determine its usefulness for detecting secular changes in the wind. It was concluded that changes in observational techniques and changes in ship routes probably preclude the possibility of gaining information on long-term changes in wind speed and direction from this data set.

In the climate area the activities planned for 1983 include a continuation of a study of equatorial Pacific cloud surges, an investigation of the reality of the secular changes suggested by the marine deck data, a study of the climatic singularity of 1963, and a study of synoptic climatology of the eastern Pacific near the Equatorial Convergence Zone.

In the area of equatorial oceanography, the Line Islands profiling project was begun as part of the PEQUOD Program. This project involves making a series of current profiles from the surface to the seafloor every $\frac{1}{2}$ degree of latitude from 3°N to 3°S at the longitude of the Line Islands. A three-month preliminary effort was carried out in the fall of 1981, and a 13-month series was begun in February 1982. This data set will be extremely valuable, not only for document-

ing the time variability of deep equatorial jets, but also for studying the oceanic dynamics of the 1982 El Niño event. Field work will conclude in 1983. Analysis of the hydrographic and current meter data from the NORPAX Hawaii-Tahiti shuttle experiment showed evidence of a vertically propagating Rossby wave. It was also concluded that the mean equatorial undercurrent is in geostrophic balance, even at the equator. In 1983 the analysis will continue of the Rossby wave data, the dynamics of the undercurrent, and Kelvin wave events of the type reported earlier. The vertical

propagation of momentum was studied in a theoretical model for Kelvin wave spin-up in a continuously stratified fluid. In 1983, we will extend these results to Rossby wave spin-up and continue investigation of the effect of coastal geometry on equatorial wave reflection. Analysis of Pacific sea-level variations and their relationships to El Niño events continued. In 1983, an El Niño rapid response capability will be developed to enable us to survey in detail the next El Niño event as soon as possible after its onset is detected.

JIMAR VISITING SCIENTISTS

Short Term

Dates	Name and Affiliation	Purpose of Visit
01/25/82-02/14/82	Dr. William J. Schmitz, Jr. Woods Hole Oceanographic Institute Woods Hole, Mass.	To present three seminars entitled, (1) The mid-latitude North-Atlantic eddy field (2) The mid-latitude North-Pacific eddy field (3) Eddy resolving numerical models: comparison with observation
01/28/82	Dr. Roger Daley NCAR Boulder, Colo.	To present a seminar entitled, "The Excitation of Large-Scale Free Rossby Waves in Numerical Weather Prediction"
01/30/82-02/15/82	Dr. Joel Picaut Laboratoire d'Océanographie Physique Université de Bretagne Occidentale Brest, France	To work with Dr. Moore and to complete work on equatorial ocean dynamics begun in summer 1981; also to present a seminar entitled, "Circulation and Production in the Equatorial Atlantic".
03/20/82-03/30/82	Dr. Harry Bryden Woods Hole Oceanographic Institute Woods Hole, Mass.	To present two seminars entitled, (1) "Ocean Heat Transport" (2) "Origin of the Mediterranean Outflow"
04/19/82	Dr. William Emery Department of Oceanography University of British Columbia Vancouver, B.C., Canada	To present a seminar entitled, "Dynamic Heights from Temperature: An Application to Historical Data and Field Tests of a Real-Time System".
04/07/82	Dr. Jürgen Willebrand (V.S. to Ocean) Max-Planck Institute for Meteorology Hamburg, Germany	To present a seminar entitled, "A Parametric Model of the Equatorial Undercurrent".

03/07/82-03/09/82

- 1) Dr. Charles Enksen, MIT
- 2) Dr. Catherine Gautier, SIO
- 3) Mr. Robert Heinmiller, Boston, MA
- 4) Dr. Robert Knox, SIO
- 5) Dr. Michael McPhaden, NCAR
- 6) Dr. Pearn Nüller, OSU

To attend the Tropic Heat Executive Meeting, in San Francisco.

JIMAR VISITING SCIENTISTS FY-1982 Long Term

Dates	Name	Former Affiliation
09/01/81-02/28/82	Dr. Motoyasu Miyata	Geophysical Institute Tokoyo University Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo, Japan

JIMAR Post-Doctoral Appointments 10/01/82-06/30/82

Dates	Name	Former Affiliation
CLIMATE RESEARCH		
06/01/81-12/14/81	Dr. Steven Lyons	University of Hawaii Department of Meteorology
EQUATORIAL OCEAN DYNAMICS		
10/01/80-08/31/82	Dr. James W. Stevenson	Harvard University
12/21/81-Present	Dr. Roger Lukas	University of Hawaii Department of Oceanography

PMEL SEMINARS

Dates	Name and Affiliation	Seminar Topic
<i>1981</i>		
22 Oct	Dr. C. Linwood Vincent Coastal Engineering Research Center U.S. Army Corps of Engineers Fort Belvoir, Virginia	"Some shallow water wave transformation results from ARSLOE (Atlantic Remote Sensing Land Ocean Experiment)."
5 Nov	Dr. W. John Gould Institute of Oceanographic Sciences Wormley, Surrey, England	"Eddy activity and seasonal effects in the NE Atlantic."
12 Nov	Dr. Miles McPhee Naches, Washington	"The effect of rapid melting on the boundary layer at the ice margin."
3 Dec	Dr. John R. Apel Pacific Marine Environmental Laboratory	"An overview of scientific results from the SEASAT program."
17 Dec	Dr. Richard Feely Pacific Marine Environmental Laboratory	"Preliminary results of the marine CO ₂ program: Carbonate dissolution studies."
<i>1982</i>		
7 Jan	Dr. L.K. Forbes Applied Mathematics Dept. University of Adelaide Australia	"Non-linear, free-surface flow over a submerged semi-elliptical body."
15 Jan	C. Steven Smyth Pacific Marine Environmental Laboratory	Satellite Oceanography Workshop
28 Jan	Dr. Alexander Malahoff Chief Scientist National Ocean Survey Rockville, Maryland	"Polymetallic sulfides of the mid-ocean ridges — the continental connection."
4 Feb	Dr. Joseph Fletcher ERL/Boulder	"Variations in the surface wind and SST over the oceans since 1860."
25 Feb	Robert Anderson Seattle Ocean Services Unit NOAA/National Weather Service	"The operations of the Seattle Ocean Services Unit."
12 Mar	David Duane Sea Grant Office, NOAA Rockville, Maryland	"The development and management of the NOAA Polymetallic Sulfide Minerals Program."

22 April	Dr. William Aron Northwest and Alaska Fisheries Center National Marine Fisheries Service, NOAA, Seattle, Washington	"Fish and the Oceans."
6 May	Dr. D. Howell Peregrine University of Bristol, England	"Refraction of nonlinear water waves: Wave jumps and caustics."
20 May	Dr. Taivo Laevastu Northwest and Alaska Fisheries Center National Marine Fisheries Service NOAA	"The effects of fishing and environmental anomalies on the fish ecosystem in the Bering Sea and Gulf of Alaska (as revealed by ecosystem simulations)."
1 June	Dr. Peter Hamilton Science Applications, Inc.	"Transport model of Puget Sound."
17 June	Edgar A. Best & Dr. Richard B. de Riso International Pacific Halibut Commission Kenneth F. Parker School of Fisheries, University of Washington	"Oceanographic effects on halibut life history."
14 July	Dr. Donald Beran PROFS Program Office NOAA/ERL, Boulder	"PROFS (Prototype Regional Observing and Forecasting Service) Program and its effects on future short-term weather forecasting."
23 July	Dr. D. Howell Peregrine Bristol University, England	"The fluid mechanics of breaking waves."

PMEL STAFF

The success of the PMEL research program is highly dependent on the talents and dedication of its staff. The permanent PMEL staff includes 32 professionals with master's or doctoral degrees, and 48 junior and support level staff. In addition, the Laboratory employs 20 staff members in positions that are other than permanent. Personnel from the NOAA Corps are given rotational assignments at PMEL in research related to their areas of expertise. Through the National Research Council Research Associateship Program, postdoctoral scientists pursue individual research in conjunction with PMEL programs for periods of up to two years. In addition, visiting scientists to JISAO and JIMAR work closely with Laboratory scientists in cooperative programs.

The Laboratory participates in several employment programs that provide opportunities for university students at both graduate and undergraduate levels to gain research experience in science and engineering. This includes the Cooperative Education Program (Coop), the Federal Junior Fellowship Program, the College Work-Study Program, and graduate research assistantships through the joint institutes.

PMEL's scientific staff is active outside the Laboratory in the local, national, and international scientific communities. Twelve Laboratory scientists hold affiliate faculty appointments at the University of Washington and two scientists hold affiliate appointments at the University of Hawaii. In this capacity, they teach graduate courses and serve on graduate committees. PMEL scientists chair or serve on the scientific steering committees for several major NOAA or interagency research programs, including EPOCS, SPOCS, STREX, POLEX, NASA Seasat Science Steering Group, International Council for Exploration of the SEA (ICES), Interunion Commission of Radio Meteorology (IUCRM), Sea Use Council, and the U.S.-U.S.S.R. Bilateral Agreement on Large-Scale Ocean-Atmospheric Studies (SCOR Working Group 56). Papers are presented at national and international professional meetings.

In FY-1982, Dr. Rudolph Preisendorfer was awarded the George J. Haltiner chair in meteorology at the Naval Postgraduate School in Monterey, California, and Dr. David Halpern was appointed Affiliate Professor in the Department of Oceanography at the University of Washington.

OFFICE OF THE DIRECTOR, Eddie N. Bernard, Acting Director

Beach, Reginald A.	Computer Operator
Borg-Breen, David R.	Computer Programmer
Jensen, Mary F.	Secretary (Stenographer)
Loomis, Harold G.	Mathematician
Lu, Paul	Computer Specialist
McCarty, Laura C.	Computer Assistant
McIntyre, Dona Rae*	Clerk-Typist
Millard, David H.	Computer Operator
Lt. (jg.) Parsons, Lawrence	Computer Specialist (NOAA Corps)
Sawyer, Constance B.*	Physical Scientist (IPS with NCAR)
Lt. Comdr. Turnbull, William	Program Specialist (NOAA Corps)
Vause, Chester A.*	NRC Post-Doctoral

TECHNICAL AND ADMINISTRATIVE SUPPORT Cynthia L. Loitsch, Program Support Officer

Anderson, James W.	Photographer (Scientific)
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PUBLICATIONS

- Baker, E.T. (1982): Suspended particulate matter in Elliott Bay. NOAA Tech. Report ERL 417-PMEL 35, Boulder, Colo., 44 pp.
- Blaha, J., and R. Reed (1982): Fluctuations of sea level in the western North Pacific and inferred flow of the Kuroshio. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, 12(7), 669-678.
- Brown, R.A., V.J. Cardone, J.E. Overland, et al. (1982): Surface wind analyses for SEASAT. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 87(5), 3355-3364.
- Byrne, H.M. (1982): The variation of the drag coefficient in the marine-surface layer due to temporal and spatial variations of the surface wind and sea state. Ph.D. diss., University of Washington.
- Cannon, G.A., and M.W. Grigsby (1982): Observations of currents and water properties in Commencement Bay. NOAA Tech. Memo. OMPA-22, 35 pp.
- Clark, D.K., E.T. Baker, and A.E. Strong (1980): Upwelled spectral radiance distribution in relation to particulate matter in sea water. *Boundary-Layer Meteorol.*, (18), 287-298.
- Cline, J.D., H.B. Milburn, and D.P. Wisegarver (1982): A simple rosette-mounted syringe sampler for the collection of dissolved gases. *Deep-Sea Res.*, Nov. 1982.
- Feely, R.A., A.J. Chester, A.J. Paulson, and J.D. Larrance (1982): Relationships between organically bound Cu and Mn in settling particulate matter and biological processes in a subarctic estuary. *Estuaries*, 5(1), 74-80.
- Feely, R.A., and G.J. Massoth (1982): Sources, composition, and transport of suspended particulate matter in lower Cook Inlet and northwestern Shelikof Strait, Alaska. NOAA Tech. Report ERL 415-PMEL 34, Boulder, Colo., 28 pp.
- Feely, R.A., G.J. Massoth, and W.M. Landig (1981): Major and trace element composition of suspended matter in the northeast Gulf of Alaska: Relationships with major sources. *Marine Chem.*, 10(5): 431-453.
- Gammon, R.H., J.D. Cline, and D. Wisegarver (1982): Chlorofluoromethanes in the northeast Pacific Ocean: measured vertical distributions and application as transient tracers of upper ocean mixing. *J. Geophys. Res.*, Nov. 1982.
- Geyer, W.R., and G.A. Cannon (1982): Sill processes related to deep-water renewal in a fjord. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 97(C10), 7985-7996.
- Gonzalez, F.I., T.W. Thompson, W.E. Brown, Jr., and D.E. Weissman (1982): SEASAT wind and wave observations of northeast Pacific hurricane IVA, August 13, 1978. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 87(C5), 3431-3438.
- Griffiths, R.P., B.A. Coldwell, J.D. Cline, W.A. Broich, and R.V. Morita (1982): Field observations of methane concentrations and oxidation rates in the southeastern Bering Sea. *App. Environ. Microbiol.*, 44(2), 435-446.
- Ikeda, M. (1981): Eddies detached from a jet crossing over a submarine ridge using a simple numerical model. NOAA Tech. Memo. ERL PMEL-33, Boulder, Colo., 38 pp.
- Ikeda, M., and J.R. Apel (1981): Mesoscale eddies detached from spatially growing meanders in an eastward-flowing oceanic jet using a two-layered quasi-geostrophic model. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, 11(12), 1638-1661.
- Ikeda, M. (1982): A simple model of subsurface mesoscale eddies. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 87(C10), 7925-7931.
- Katz, C.N., J.D. Cline, and K. Kelly-Hansen (1982): Dissolved methane concentrations in the southeastern Bering Sea, 1980 and 1981. NOAA Data Report, ERL PMEL-6, Boulder, Colo., July 1982, 194 pp.
- Larsen, J.C. (1982): Electromagnetic Transport Measurements of the Florida Current, Proceedings of the IEEE Second Working Conference of Current Measurements, W. Woodward and M. Dursy, eds. Hilton Head, S.C.
- Lavelle, J.W., E. Ozturgut, E.T. Baker, S.A. Swift (1982): Discharge and surface plume measurements during manganese nodule mining tests in the North Equatorial Pacific. *Marine Environ. Res.*, 7, 51-70.
- Lavelle, J.W., and D.J.P. Swift (1982): Near-shore currents measured in ridge-and-swale topography off Long Island, New York. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 87(C6), 4190-4194.
- Lindsay, R.W., and A.L. Comiskey (1982): Surface and upper-air observations in the eastern Bering Sea. NOAA Tech. Memo. ERL PMEL-35, Boulder, Colo., 90 pp.
- Liu, C.T. (1982): Analysis of tropical Pacific sea surface temperatures for 1975 to 1980. NOAA Tech. Memo. ERL PMEL-34, 160 pp.
- Massoth, G.J., R.A. Feely, and M.F. Lamb (1982): Trace element composition of suspended particulate matter in the lower Duwamish River and Elliott Bay, Washington. NOAA Tech. Memo. OMPA-17, Boulder, Colo., 41 pp.
- Mulhern, M.R. (1982): current measurements in the Columbia River estuary. Dept. of Civil Engineering, University of Washington, Master's Report, 60 pp.
- Overland, J.E., and C.H. Pease (1982): Cyclone climatology of the Bering Sea and its relation to sea ice extent. *Mon. Wea. Rev.*, 10(1), 5-13.
- Overland, J.E., and R.W. Preisendorfer (1982): A significance test for principal components applied to a cyclone climatology. *Mon. Wea. Rev.*, 110(1), 1-4.
- Ozturgut, E., J.W. Lavelle, and B.H. Erickson (1981): Estimated discharge characteristics of a commercial nodule mining operation. *Mar. Mining*, 3(1,2), 1-7.
- Pazan, S.E., T.P. Barnett, D. Halpern, and A.M. Tubbs (1982): Comparison of observed and model wind velocities. *J. Appl. Meteor.*, 21, 314-320.
- Pease, C.H., S.A. Schoenberg, J.E. Overland (1982): A climatology of the Bering Sea and its relation to sea ice extent. NOAA Tech. report, ERL 419-PMEL 36, 29 pp.
- Preisendorfer, R.W. (1982): *Empirical Orthogonal Functions Viewed in Terms of Pearson's Lines and Planes of Best Fit*. SIO Ref. Series 81-, Scripps Inst. Oceanogr., Jan. 1981.
- Preisendorfer, R.W. (1982): *Cumulative Probability Tables for Eigenvalues of Random Covariance Matrices*. SIO Ref. Series 81-2, Scripps Inst. Oceanogr., Feb. 1981.
- Preisendorfer, R.W. (1982): *Asymptotic Eigenvalue Curves of Random Covariance matrices*. SIO Ref. Series 81-3, Scripps Inst. Oceanogr., April 1981.
- Preisendorfer, R.W., and C.D. Mobley (1982): Climate forecast verifications, Climate forecast verifications, U.S. mainland, 1974-82. NOAA Tech. Memo. ERL PMEL-36, Boulder, Colo., 236 pp.
- Preisendorfer, R.W., F.W. Zwiers, T.P. Barnett (1982): *Foundations of Principal Component Selection Rules*. SIO Ref. Series 81-4, Scripps Inst. of Oceanogr., May 1981, 192 pp.
- Pullen, P.E., and H.M. Byrne (1981): Hydrographic measurements during the 1978 Cooperative Soviet-American Tsunami Expedition, NOAA Data Report ERL PMEL-4, Boulder, Colo., October 1981.
- Reed, R.K. (1982): Comparison of measured and estimated insolation over the eastern Pacific Ocean. *J. of Appl. Met.* 21(3), 339-341.
- Reed, R.K. (1982): Reply. *J. of Appl. Met.*, 21(1), 114-5.
- Reed, R.K. (1982): Energy fluxes over the eastern tropic Pacific Ocean, 1979-1982. NOAA Tech. Rep. ERL 422-PMEL 37, Boulder, Colo., 15 pp.

Reynolds, R.M. (1982): Comparison of surface meteorological observations from ship and toroid buoy in the North Pacific during STREX, *J. Appl. Meteorol.*, 12, 1032-1037.

Salo, S.A., L.K. Coachman, and J.D. Schumacher (1982): Winter currents on the eastern Bering Sea shelf, *BOS Transactions, AGU*, 63, 100.

Schumacher, J.D., C.A. Pearson, and J.E. Overland (1982): On exchange of water between the Gulf of Alaska and the Bering Sea through Unimak Pass. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 87(C7), 5785-5795.

Taft, B.A., P. Kovala, and A. Cantos-Figueroa (1982): Vertical sections of temperature, salinity, thermocline anomaly and zonal geostrophic velocity from NORPAX Shuttle Experiment — Part 2. NOAA Data Report ERL PMEL-5, Boulder, Colo., 94 pp.

Wald, L., J.M. Monget, M. Albuissou, H.M. Byrne (1982): A large-scale monitoring of the hydrocarbons pollution from the Landsat satellite, in *Proceedings of NATO/CCMS Workshop*, Paris, October 12-6, 1982.

Glossary of Acronyms

CMOS: Complementary Metal Oxide Substrate

CTD: Conductivity, Temperature, Depth

CUEA: Coastal Upwelling Ecosystem Analysis

DOMES: Deep Ocean Mining Environmental Study

EOF: Empirical Orthogonal Function

EPOCS: NOAA Equatorial Pacific Ocean Climate Studies

EQUA: PMEL Equatorial Studies Program

FRONTS: Study of Large-Scale Frontal Zones

GC-MS: Gas Chromatograph-Mass Spectrometer

GEM-GOES: GOES Environmental Monitor-Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite

GOASEX: Gulf of Alaska Seasat Experiment

GOES: Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite

ICES: International Council for Exploration of the Sea

ITCZ: Intertropical Convergence Zone

IUCRM: Inter-Union Commission on Radio Meteorology

JASIN: Joint Air-Sea Interaction Experiment

JIMAR: Joint Institute for Marine & Atmospheric Research

JISAO: Joint Institute for the Study of Atmosphere & Ocean

JTRE: Joint Tsunami Research Effort

L-RERP: Long-Range Effects Research Program

MESA: Marine Ecosystems Analysis

MILE: Mixed Layer Experiment

MIZEX: Marginal Ice Zone Experiment

NECC: North Equatorial Countercurrent

NMFS: National Marine Fisheries Service

NOS: National Ocean Survey

NORPAX: North Pacific Experiment

NSCC: Northern Subsurface Countercurrent

NSF: National Science Foundation

NWS: National Weather Service

OARS: Ocean Acoustic Remote Sensing

OCSEAP: Outer Continental Shelf Environmental Assessment Program

OMPA: Office of Marine Pollution Assessment

PVC: Polyvinyl Chloride

PTG: Pressure Temperature Gauge

RJE: Remote Job Entry

SAR: Synthetic Aperture Radar

SCOR: Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research

SEC: South Equatorial Current

SLAR: Side-Looking Airborne Radar

SOPS: Simplified Ocean Profiling System

SPM: Suspended-Particulate Matter

STACS: Subtropical Atlantic Climate Study

STREX: Storm Transfer and Response Experiment

SST: Sea Surface Temperature

TD: Dewpoint temperature

TOPS: Total Ocean Profiling System

UCM: Unresolved Complex Mixture

UV-B: Ultraviolet-B

VACM: Vector-Averaging Current Meter

XTVP: Expendable Temperature Velocity Profiler

XBT: Expendable Bathythermograph

